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Authors: Ximena Rueda (UoA), Nicolás Mejía (UoA), Truly Santika (UoG), Joseph Hitimana (UoK), Martin Tchamba (UoD), Kirsten de Beurs (WU), Noah Kibet (UoK), Dorothy Masiga Syallow (UoK), Princely Nyong (UoD), Jack E. Odongo Ogembo (UoK), George Omondi (UoK), Lucie Temgoua (UoD), Herman Zanguim (UoD), A. Vandenbussche (WU), Verina Ingram (WU).

Reviewers: Valerie Nelson (UoG), Verina Ingram (WU)

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Abstract

The Transformative Change for Biodiversity and Equity (TCforBE) project (2022 – 2026) conducts transdisciplinary research to co-generate transformative change pathways in the context of telecoupled agrifood systems. It engages diverse stakeholders and explores plural perspectives within the EU and partner countries of Cameroon, Colombia, and Kenya, including EU and national policymakers, Indigenous Peoples and local communities. The project aims to strengthen stakeholder capacity on transformative change pathways leading to enhanced biodiversity and equity outcomes. Work package (WP) 4 provides an analysis of producer country transformative governance pathways.

In this first deliverable of work package 4, we present the results of that analysis for three biodiversity-rich countries in the global South - Cameroon, Colombia, and Kenya - that are linked through trade, aid and other policies to the European Union, its companies, and its consumers. This report presents a descriptive analysis of land use change and commodity expansion during the 2010-2020 period for the main agricultural crops traded in those countries, together with a spatially explicit typology of landscape patterns and processes, utilizing geospatial open-source datasets, long-term land use Earth Observation data, and (sub)national datasets, alongside a spatially explicit typology of landscape patterns and processes. Biodiversity risks associated with these telecoupled commodities are also assessed by analysing the relationship between the change in crop area within relevant spatial or administrative unit in each country every five years with the change in each of the biodiversity indicators. An overview is provided of sustainable landscape initiatives and the discourses on biodiversity and agriculture in each country.

Based on these results, the team will develop the subsequent deliverables of WP4, analysing the role of different policy interventions on fostering agricultural growth (Deliverable 4.2) to identify possible areas for policy interventions that could be discussed with policy makers and interested parties to foster the transition towards more sustainable land uses and trade policies, and in Deliverable 5.4 on sustainable landscape initiatives.

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Glossary

See [TC4BE glossary](#) for key terms and definitions.

Background

TCforBE aims and objectives

Demand for agricultural commodities from EU agrifood systems is driving land use change in biodiversity-rich countries in the Global South, leading to major biodiversity losses. Globalisation processes have led to increases in EU imports of commodities such as coffee and palm oil. EU trade has become increasingly 'telecoupled', i.e. characterised by distant, coupled human and natural systems via highly inequitable global value chains, which have extensive socioeconomic and environmental impacts.

Tackling the EU's global biodiversity footprint is a top EU policy priority. Transformative change pathways are needed for safe and just transitions; but there are plural perspectives on what might constitute transformative change for food territories and systems, including telecoupled ones, and how to achieve it. New EU policies, such as Farm to Fork, may significantly re-shape agrifood trade between the EU and producer countries, with a range of potential implications for employment, livelihoods, but also equity, justice, and biodiversity. Much depends upon the purpose of the food system or territory, but there is contestation on potential food futures at different scales. There are increasing calls for systemic levers, but barriers to action are significant.

The Transformative Change for Biodiversity and Equity (TCforBE) project, (2022 – 2026), will support transdisciplinary research to co-generate transformative change pathways in the context of telecoupled agrifood systems. It will engage diverse stakeholders and explore plural perspectives within the EU and partner countries of Cameroon, Colombia and Kenya, including EU and national policymakers and Indigenous Peoples and local communities. The project aims to strengthen stakeholder capacity on transformative change pathways leading to enhanced biodiversity and equity outcomes.

The project aims to inform policy discourse, e.g. the EU's Green Deal implementation, and especially the Farm to Fork Strategy, which aims to reduce the environmental and climate footprint of the EU food system and its climate resilience, and specifically responds to expert scientific advice that highlights a particular need for more social science evidence on **how to achieve a sustainable food system**. The project will generate such evidence, as well as contributions from and to environmental science on biodiversity measurement and valuation. The project will also engage national policymakers and seek to inform landscape stewardship strategies in study landscapes in Africa and Latin America.

TCforBE contributes to four HORIZON EUROPE specific outcomes: 1) Sustainable pathways, 2) human dimensions, 3) social norms, behaviours, values, and 4) inform/motivate transformational change. The project work packages (WPs) address all the outcomes in a cross-cutting way and are arranged according to *scale of interest* (e.g. EU and global, national producer countries, landscape levels).

There are seven **work packages** addressing the project's specific objectives (Box 1), each with associated results and deliverables:

- WP 1 will generate insights on EU policies and societal shifts under new green policies in relation to food systems and modelling of potential impacts on relevant biomes.
- WP 2 explores transformative governance arrangements and levers for change. This includes analysis of trade and legal levers, social movements and collective action, and

biodiversity governance initiatives, as well as identifying the best ways to engage with EU and other scale learning and communications stakeholders.

- WP 3 will summarise the taxonomy and related regulations targeting and enabling Biodiversity measurement and develop sustainable finance pathways that are aggregable and scalable to impact and transform current mainstream finance logics.
- WP4 will examine three case study LMIC countries —Cameroon, Colombia, and Kenya—to investigate how national biodiversity, agricultural, and economic policies influence biodiversity and equity outcomes. The analysis will also assess how these outcomes are shaped by international environmental governance, identifying the ways in which it enables or constrains national policy efforts.
- WP 5 – landscape scale engagement and research - activities as in WP4, but the transformative change pathways will include generation of a Bayesian tool drawing on Q methodology and social learning, corporate/regen case studies, rural imaginaries (political ecology and ethnography).
- WP 6 will involve a conceptual framing, but also synthesis of findings and support for inter-landscape and global / EU dialogues on transformative change pathways.
- WP 7 concerns management, dissemination and communication of the project.

All work packages will engage with communications, WP7 has a particular focus on making the knowledge, tools and methods generated by the project available to global audiences through appropriate media, to inform policy dialogues and learning. The transformative change pathways for landscape approaches, will be shared with and disseminated to policymakers, researchers, and agrifood system stakeholders.

TCforBE overall approach

The overall approach is underpinned by **multi-stakeholder social learning cycles** and ensuring attention is given to plural values. The researchers will seek to cogenerate and co-analyse transformative change pathways at different scales for highly telecoupled landscapes and to facilitate dialogues between landscape actors and national and EU level stakeholders. To inform these learning cycles and dialogues, researcher driven activities will enrich the landscape and national level learning processes and contribute to an overall analysis of transformative change pathways in telecoupled contexts (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Components of the TCforBE Project

The envisaged research and learning activities include:

- Conceptual work on transformative change and biodiversity and equity pathways in telecoupled food and agriculture contexts, and synthesis and analysis of findings.
- Generation of scenarios and modelling of EU agrifood systems transformations. Understanding the potential implications of EU policy and societal transitions for low- and middle-income countries that link to the EU through telecoupling is vital as dietary shifts are already occurring and policy decisions are being made which may reduce or change EU country sourcing patterns.
- Exploration of plural perspectives on transformative change at EU, national and landscape scales through qualitative research.
- Analysis of interconnected processes and levers including EU biodiversity governance, trade, legal, consumer, collective action and sustainable finance levers and social innovations.)
- Analysis and social learning on plural perspectives on transformative change at national scale and identification of land use change drivers (e.g. commodity impacts, at-risk biodiversity hotspots, and sustainable landscape initiative impacts.)
- Social learning cycles at landscape scale: participant-driven learning to co-generate transformative change pathways for food systems and territories (creative learning activities) and to inform/reflect upon planned researcher-led activities.

Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AFA	Agriculture and Food Authority
CEMAC	Central African Economic and Monetary Community
CIRAD	French Agricultural Research Centre for International Development
ERS	Economic Recovery Strategy of Kenya
EU	European Union
EVA	Agricultural Municipal Evaluations of Colombia (<i>Evaluaciones Agropecuarias Municipales</i>)
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
FEDEGAN	Colombian Federation of Cattlemen (<i>Federación Colombiana de Ganaderos</i>)
FPEAK	Fresh Producers and Exporters Association of Kenya
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GoK	Government of Kenya
HCD	Horticultural Crops Development
HeCo	Integrated Landscape Management supported by the European Union in Colombia (<i>Herencia Colombia</i>)
IGAC	Geographical statistics institute of Colombia (<i>Instituto Agustín Codazzi</i>)
ILM	Integrated Landscape Management
KTDA	Kenya Tea Development Authority
MINADER	Ministry of Agriculture of Cameroon
MINAGRICULTURA	Ministry of Agriculture of Colombia
OMECA	Colombian's conservation Area (Otras Medidas de Conservación Basadas en Áreas)
SLI	Sustainable Landscape Initiatives
SRA	Sector Recovery Action Plan of Kenya
WWF	World Wildlife Fund

2. Introduction

The European Union (EU) is a major importer of tropical commodities such as palm oil, coffee, cacao and bananas (WWF 2021). As globalization intensifies, the demand for commodities in biodiversity-rich countries in the Global South has risen, creating market opportunities but also exerting increased pressure and posing biodiversity threats (Lenzen et al. 2012). This dynamic has contributed to a global biodiversity crisis, linked to complex agri-food systems.

Food and trade systems can be analysed using a telecoupling lens (Hermans et al 2023) to reveal not only the economic connections in commodity value chains but also the intricate socioeconomic and environmental impacts, as well as the governance challenges of such interactions. Unpacking these connections is necessary to address the root causes of biodiversity loss and the equity dimension of global trade, and to propose integral recommendations that address the complex and multiple connections, the diversity of the actors involved and the multiscale impacts of specific actions.

Addressing the EU's biodiversity global footprint is a top priority for policymakers and agro-food stakeholders globally, necessitating transformative changes in economic, social, and financial models. To achieve this, understanding historical patterns of agricultural behaviour in the Global South is crucial. This involves examining the dynamics of agricultural expansion and its connections to international markets.

This report presents the findings of an analysis on biodiversity dynamics in three Global South countries—Cameroon, Colombia, and Kenya—that share trade, aid, and policy linkages with the European Union, its industries, and its consumers. The analysis is conducted at two levels: nationally and within specific landscapes of interest in each country. At the national level, the report examines commodity expansion trends from 2010 to 2020, focusing on major agricultural crops involved in trade. It also develops a spatially explicit typology of landscape patterns and processes. At the landscape level, a biodiversity risk analysis is undertaken, exploring the impacts associated with telecoupled tropical commodities. The study utilizes geospatial open-source datasets, long-term Earth observation data on land use, and (sub)national datasets to conduct these analyses. The report is structured as follows: Chapter 1 provides an introduction; Chapter 2 outlines the methodology; Chapter 3 presents the primary findings for each country, covering both levels of analysis; and Chapter 4 discusses the limitations of the study.

A more detailed analysis of the direct quantitative impacts of commodity-driven biodiversity loss on specific ecosystems will be presented in **Deliverable 4.2**. This forthcoming deliverable will quantitatively link the drivers, commodities, and landscape changes, incorporating the effects of policies and other external factors. It will address key questions, including: (a) How has the spatial distribution of financial investments supporting commodity production shifted over time, and how have these shifts responded to fluctuations in international commodity prices? (b) How have financial support mechanisms, combined with land formalization, influenced the expansion of commodity production, while accounting for underlying biophysical and socioeconomic conditions? (c) What are the biodiversity risks associated with commodity expansion?

Cameroon, Colombia, and Kenya have significant linkages with the European Union through aid, making it essential to review the primary EU-supported Sustainable Landscapes Initiatives (SLIs). This review will identify where these initiatives are located and examine their connection to agricultural frontier expansion. This analysis of the SLIs falls within the scope of WP5, specifically **Deliverable 5.4**, which involves landscape-level assessments of: (a) the impacts of commodity production, and (b) the effectiveness of SLIs in promoting biodiversity conservation, ecosystem restoration, and equity. Within the selected Innovation Landscapes, the project team will develop a Bayesian hierarchical modelling tool to assess how agrofood commodity production and trade, along with specific SLIs, affect biodiversity, livelihoods, and food security outcomes.

3. Methodology and data

To our knowledge, this multi-criteria and multi-method analysis of land use changes, agricultural patterns trade and landuse patterns and processes has not previously been conducted for these countries, making it a novel contribution to understanding the drivers and implications of agricultural change in each region. This approach sheds light on current trends and sets the stage for more targeted analyses of how agricultural expansion impacts environmental and socioeconomic factors in each country and landscape.

This work draws on Geist and Lambin's (2002) work that summarized the main proximate and distal drivers of land use change and was later updated to integrate the effects of globalization and supply chain dynamics on land use change (Lambin and Meyfroidt 2011). This framework constitutes the basis of the work of the Land Change Science community (GLP, 2023), and allows us to systematically tackle the different drivers of land use change and the underlying causes, shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Drivers of land use change and underlying causes

The TcforBE project focuses on agricultural expansion and its associated socioeconomic, geophysical, transport, and institutional factors while outlining all deforestation drivers in the tropics. This deliverable 4.1 specifically examines the primary influences of biodiversity change linked to agricultural expansion.

This report is structured according to countries pertinent to the project, namely Cameroon, Kenya, and Colombia with two to three key export commodities examined per country in terms of (i) changes in distribution and (ii) the risk that commodity production poses to biodiversity. Based on a literature review followed by the land use analysis (section 2.1), we focused on timber, cocoa, and oil palm in Cameroon; tea and avocado in Kenya; and banana, coffee, and oil palm in Colombia.

2.1 Land use

To analyze historical agricultural patterns from 2010 to 2020, we focus on identifying the main crops in each country using three key criteria. This approach allows us to gain a comprehensive

understanding of agricultural dynamics by concentrating on the crops that have the greatest impact on land use and export activities.

- a) The first criterion targets crops that collectively account for up to 80% of total agricultural land in each country in 2020, shown in Tables 1 to 3). This threshold is inspired by the Pareto principle, which suggests that a small number of factors drive most land use change outcomes. By focusing on crops that dominate agricultural land use, we aimed to better understand the primary forces shaping landscapes.
- b) The second criterion includes crops that have experienced the most substantial growth in cultivated area over the study period. By identifying crops with the greatest expansion, we can track shifting agricultural priorities and potential responses to domestic or international market demands, as well as environmental or policy changes. This growth metric highlights emerging agricultural trends and potential pressures on land resources.
- c) The third criterion focuses on crops with a strong export profile, selecting those that play a crucial role in each country's trade portfolio. Examining export-oriented crops provides insight into how agricultural production aligns with global market demands and the role of international trade in shaping local agricultural practices.

Table 1 Major crops covering 80% of Cameroon's cultivated area in 2020, with respective percentage shares

Crop	2020	Percentage of total production
Corn	1.169.941	17,10%
Sorghum	740.000	10,82%
Cocoa	578.736	8,46%
Peanut	516.904	7,56%
Plantain	506.440	7,40%
Yucca	401.959	5,88%
Beans	302.571	4,42%
Cucumber	275.333	4,02%
Cotton	225.000	3,29%
Cowpeas	221.929	3,24%
Oil palm	219.683	3,21%
Taro (cocoyam)	218.017	3,19%
Pumpkin	152.444	2,23%

Source: FAOSTAT 2024, Own Calculations

Table 2 Major crops covering 80% of Colombia's cultivated area in 2020, with respective percentage shares

Crop	2020	Percentage of total production
Coffee	844.744	19,31%
Rice	656.000	14,99%
Oil palm	478.045	10,93%
Sugar cane	407.583	9,32%
Corn	345.069	7,89%
Plantain	264.106	6,04%
Cocoa	188.371	4,31%
Potatoes	125.426	2,87%
Banana	99.267	2,27%
Yucca	97.074	2,22%

Source: FAOSTAT 2024, Own Calculations

Table 3 Major Crops Covering 80% of Kenya's Cultivated Area in 2020, with Respective Percentage Shares

Crop	2020	Percentage of total production
Corn	2.135.741	36,00%
Beans	1.147.709	19,35%
Tea	269.400	4,54%
Cowpeas	239.131	4,03%
Sorghum	219.657	3,70%
Potatoes	176.252	2,97%
Pigeon peas	133.525	2,25%
Wheat	132.231	2,23%
Coffee	119.700	2,02%

Source: FAOSTAT 2024, Own Calculations

For **Cameroon**, national-level data on cultivated hectares, production, and crop exports for each year were obtained from FAOSTAT, with detailed insights provided by the Ministry of Agriculture (MINADER).

For **Colombia**, municipal-level data on cultivated hectares per crop were drawn from the Agricultural Municipal Evaluations (EVA) conducted by the Ministry of Agriculture (MINAGRICULTURA). Data on livestock numbers at the departmental level were provided by FEDEGAN, the Colombian Federation of Cattlemen. However, detailed records of hectares designated for livestock activities were unavailable for all study years. To address this gap, the Colombian Geographical Statistics Institute (IGAC) provided calculations for 2017, which were used as a baseline to estimate the hectares for subsequent years based on herd size, assuming a constant livestock density.

In **Kenya**, agricultural production and trade data was compiled from governmental and industry sources, including the Agriculture and Food Authority (AFA), Horticultural Crops Development (HCD), Fresh Producers and Exporters Association of Kenya (FPEAK), Kenya Tea Development Authority (KTDA), and the Kenya National Bureau of Statistics.

2.2 Trade patterns

We assessed whether key agricultural commodities are primarily directed toward international markets or intended for domestic consumption, to understand their telecoupling levels—how local agricultural systems are linked to distant economic and environmental processes. This analysis helps us evaluate the impact of international trade on agricultural expansion, particularly in terms of how external market demand influences land use and crop production patterns within the study countries.

To achieve this, we analyzed production volumes and export quantities for each selected crop in both 2010 and 2020. By comparing these figures, we calculate the production-to-export ratio, which reveals the percentage of total agricultural production that is exported. This ratio provides important insights into the role of global trade in shaping agricultural priorities, highlighting the degree to which certain crops are oriented toward international markets.

In addition to calculating the production-to-export ratio, we map trade flows for each crop, identifying the percentage of exports directed toward specific destination countries. This mapping allows us to examine the global trade networks surrounding each commodity, shedding light on how international demand influences agricultural production in the countries under study. By tracing the flow of goods, we can better understand the economic connections between these nations and their trading partners, and assess the broader implications of international trade on agricultural landscapes, local economies, and biodiversity.

2.3 Commodity distribution changes

The change in commodity distribution was assessed every five years between 2000 and 2020, subject to data availability.

For **Cameroon**, timber data was obtained from the Global Forest Watch (GFW) database (<https://data.globalforestwatch.org/datasets/minfop::concessions-forestieres>), cocoa from MapSPAM (<https://mapspam.info>, IFPRI 2019), and oil palm from a recent publication by Descals et al. (2024) (<https://zenodo.org/records/11034131>). Data for timber and oil palm were available every five years between 2000 and 2020, however data for cocoa were only available between 2005 and 2015. These commodity datasets are available at the farm boundary (for timber) or pixel level (for cocoa and oil palm). The distribution of commodities was subsequently aggregated to the arrondissement level, Cameroon's third administrative level after regions and departments. There are 360 arrondissements in the country.

Data for tea cultivation in **Kenya** were obtained from MapSPAM, while avocados were obtained from the Horticulture Validated Report published by the Agriculture and Food Authority of Kenya (<https://statistics.kilimo.go.ke>). Tea data was available from 2005 to 2015, while avocado data was available from 2010 to 2020. Tea data was originally available at the pixel level, but they were aggregated to the constituency level, Kenya's third administrative level after counties and sub-counties. Avocado data was only available at the county level, capturing the hectare of land area utilized for avocado farming. There are 47 counties and 290 constituencies in the country.

For **Colombia**, data on banana, coffee, and oil palm were obtained from the Agricultural Municipal Evaluations (EVA) conducted by the Ministry of Agriculture (MINAGRICULTURA). All statistics were available from 2007 to 2020. The data reported the total land area in each municipality used for crop agriculture. There are 1,122 municipalities in the country.

2.4 Value chains

We use value chains as a concept for analysis. Tropical agricultural supply changes are a key example of telecoupling because they link producers in the global south with consumers around the globe. Agrifood value chains vary depending on the type of product, the actors involved, the market conditions, and the institutional environment. Dimensions that commonly differ and create different impacts and use and biodiversity are:

- I. The degree of integration and coordination among the different actors in the chain, such as farmers, traders, processors, retailers, and consumers. Some chains may be more fragmented and competitive, while others may be more consolidated and cooperative. The level of integration and coordination may affect the efficiency, quality, and sustainability of the chain (Farm Radio International, 2012)
- II. The scale and structure of production, which may range from smallholder farms to large plantations, or a combination of both. The scale and structure of production may influence the productivity, profitability, and resilience of the chain, as well as the social and environmental impacts. (Norton, 2014; Dubey et al., 2022)
- III. The type and level of value addition, which refers to the transformation of the raw product into a more processed and differentiated product that meets the needs and preferences of the consumers. Value addition may occur at different stages of the chain, such as on-farm, at local processing facilities, or at industrial plants. Value addition may enhance the competitiveness, profitability, and quality of the chain, but may also require more investment, skills, and technology (FAO, 2014)
- IV. The market orientation and destination, which may be local, national, regional, or global. The market orientation and destination may determine the demand, price, and standards for the product, as well as the opportunities and challenges for the chain actors to mitigate

impacts. Some chains provision multiple markets, while others may specialize in niche markets (FAO, 2014).

For example for palm oil from Cameroon, a mixed of semi-wild harvesting, small holders, informal industrial and formal industrial plantations coexist (Orday et al. 2017), and a large informal trade exists alongside some large plantations and mills. Cocoa production in Cameroon and Colombia is conducted by small holders who are linked together in cooperatives or large groups and coexists with traders and large multinational buyers (Herve and Zhao 2019), adopting a typical hour-glass structure of concentration as the product moves down the value chain.

2.5 Landscape patterns and processes

To analyze significant landscape patterns and processes, we developed a spatially explicit typology using the Tropical Moist Forests (TMF) dataset¹. This dataset provides detailed, wall-to-wall maps with a high spatial resolution of 30 meters, classifying land cover into the following typologies:

- Intact Forest: Undisturbed primary forests.
- Deforestation: Permanent land cover change from forest to non-forested land.
- Degradation: Temporary disturbances within forests that remain forested, caused by factors such as selective logging, fires, or extreme weather events (e.g., hurricanes, droughts, blowdowns).
- Forest Regrowth: Recovery of forested areas following deforestation.
- Water: Areas occupied by water bodies.
- Non-Forest Land: Areas with non-forest registers.

Using this dataset, we analyzed changes in the proportion of land area within each land cover category at the department level across three countries, examining trends every decade from 1990 to 2020. Additionally, we proposed a new typology to classify forest transition categories over the same period. This typology evaluates land cover dynamics across four key categories: intact forest, secondary forest, non-forest land, and degraded/deforested areas.

2.5 Biodiversity risks associated with telecoupled tropical commodities

To quantify the biodiversity risk associated with commodity production, we used two indicators to represent pressure on biodiversity: (i) changes in forest or tree cover, and (ii) species vulnerability. While forest or tree cover is widely used to represent biodiversity value, it can underestimate the importance of regions with high biodiversity value but limited above-ground biomass, such as the savanna ecosystem. To address this issue, we included a second metric that measures species vulnerability, determined by combining species richness and the degree of landscape modification or pressure. With this metric, regions exhibiting both high species richness and significant landscape pressure are at greater risk for biodiversity loss compared to regions with low species richness and high landscape pressure, or those with high species richness and limited pressure.

Data on tree cover change every five years between 2000 and 2020 were obtained from the Tropical Moist Forests (TMF) database². The data are provided at a 30 m spatial resolution and originally included six land classifications: undisturbed forest, degraded forest, deforested, regrowth, non-forest, and water. We then classified trees as undisturbed forest, degraded forest, or regrowth. These data were aggregated to relevant spatial or administrative unit in each country.

¹ <https://forobs.jrc.ec.europa.eu/TMF>

² <https://forobs.jrc.ec.europa.eu/TMF>

Data on species richness were obtained from the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) database³. This data represents the total number of various amphibian, bird, mammal, and reptile species per unit area. Data on current landscape pressure were obtained from the Global Human Modification dataset⁴. This data represents the estimated degree of landscape pressure from agriculture, mining, energy production, human settlement, and electrical infrastructure (Theobald et al. 2020). The data contains values ranging from 0 to 1, with 0 indicating undisturbed natural habitats and 1 indicating substantial landscape change. Both the species richness and landscape pressure datasets were aggregated to the relevant geographical or administrative unit in each country. The species richness vulnerability metric for each administrative unit was then calculated by first categorising the species richness and landscape disturbance data into four ordered groups based on percentile, and then multiplying the results.

The risk that each commodity production posed to biodiversity was assessed by analysing the relationship between the change in crop area within relevant spatial or administrative unit in each country every five years with the change in each of the biodiversity indicators. An ordinary linear regression was used to assess the significance of the relationship.

Caveat. An important caveat about using species richness as a biodiversity indicator is that this indicator places a greater emphasis on the number of species, regardless of endemism or sensitivity to environmental change. Some landscapes or ecosystems contain a greater number of endemic species that are more susceptible to environmental pressures, and these habitats possess high biodiversity value that may contribute to the overall functioning of larger ecosystems. Agricultural development in these areas may therefore result in a larger loss of biodiversity and ecosystem overall.

2.6 Literature review

A search of scientific peer reviewed, and grey literature (including websites) were used to identify Sustainable Landscape Initiatives (SLIs), drivers of land use, commodity distribution and trade and discourses about biodiversity and agriculture changes.

A SLI was defined as an approach which is a multi-stakeholder collaborative strategy to advance shared sustainability goals and build resilience at landscape scale. A jurisdictional approach is a landscape approach defined by administrative boundaries and with a high level of government involvement. SLIs are on-the-ground collaborative programs that set common goals, take collective action while reconciling different interests, and monitor progress towards improving social, environmental, and economic outcomes at a landscape/jurisdictional scale.

³ <https://www.iucnredlist.org/resources/other-spatial-downloads>

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3963013>

4. Results

3.1 Cameroon

3.1.1 Land use

Agriculture is the mainstay of Cameroon's economy, engaging an estimated 70 percent of the economically active population and accounting for an estimated 80 percent of the primary sector's contribution to the country's GDP (AfDB, 2022). Agriculture faces many challenges, such as low productivity, poor infrastructure, climate change, and food insecurity. However, the government and its partners have launched several initiatives to boost agricultural production and value addition, as well as to improve the livelihoods and resilience of rural communities (International Trade Administration, 2021; AfDB, 2022; WWF, 2023). Some of the initiatives that aim to expand agriculture in Cameroon include:

- The Agricultural Production Support Program, funded by the African Development Bank and aims to increase the production and productivity of six priority crops (maize, cassava, plantain, sorghum, groundnut, and rice) and three livestock products (poultry, pig, and small ruminants) in six regions of the country.
- The Food and Agriculture Program, implemented by WWF Cameroon aims to promote sustainable agriculture and aquaculture that conserve biodiversity, enhance climate resilience, and benefit rural communities. The program focuses on supporting the development of a sustainable palm oil sector, as well as improving the management of fisheries and aquaculture resources.
- The Agricultural Equipment Program, which is supported by the International Trade Administration and aims to increase the access and use of modern and efficient agricultural equipment, such as tractors, harvesters, irrigation systems, and processing machines, by Cameroonian farmers and agribusinesses.
- The Project for the Improvement of the Resilience of Rural Communities to Climate Change in the West region, is financed by the World Bank and aims to improve the access to water, sanitation, hygiene, and health services, prevent and treat diseases related to climate change,
- The 2011 Support Program for the Improvement of Agricultural Productivity, National Indicative Program 2014-2020, and the 2014 "Horizon 2020 Recovery and Development Plan for Cocoa and Coffee Value Chains" aim to double national cocoa production to 600,000 tons of cocoa beans annually by 2020 (Office of the Prime Minister, 2014). This objective was not achieved and was postponed to 2030.
- The Ministry of Research and Innovation (MINRESI) and the Agricultural Research Institute for Development (IRAD) have focused on increasing the quantity and quality of cocoa production pre- and post-harvest. In February 2023 a multi-stakeholder consultation platform "Sustainable Cocoa Committee in Cameroon" between MINADER and MINCommerce and public and private sector, civil society, and research representatives, aimed to implement the "Roadmap to deforestation free cocoa", an initiative financed and supported by the Dutch Sustainable Trade Initiative (IDH) (IDH, 2021, 2023).

Table 1 shows the area and production per crop (cocoa, coffee, oil palm, plantain, banana, maize) for 2010, 2015 and 2020. In 2020, the crops that accounted for 80% of the harvested area in Cameroon included corn, sorghum, cocoa, peanut, plantain, cassava, beans, cucumber, cotton, cowpeas, oil palm, taro (cocoyam), and pumpkin. Among these crops, sorghum, cocoa, and cowpeas experienced a decrease in harvested area over the period from 2010 to 2020. Out of these crops, only cocoa and cotton had exports representing a significant portion of total production, with cocoa at 84% and cotton at 14% in 2020 (Table 4).

Table 4. Comparison between 2010 and 2020 in terms of area, production, exports, and the export-to-production ratio for crops representing 80% of the cultivated area, Cameroon.

Crop	Harvested area (ha)	Production (tons)	Exports (tons)	Exports/Production		
Corn	2010	846.130	1.670.321	4.657	0,28	%
	2020	1.169.941	2.087.957	725	0,03	%
	2010-2020 change	38,27%	25,00%	-84,44%	-0,24	pp.pp
Sorghum	2010	763.883	1.098.500	N.D	N.D	%
	2020	740.000	1.200.000	7.660	0,64	%
	2010-2020 change	-3,13%	9,24%	N.D	N.D	pp.pp
Cocoa	2010	670.000	264.077	213.267	80,76	%
	2020	578.736	280.077	237.843	84,92	%
	2010-2020 change	-13,62%	6,06%	11,52%	4,16	pp.pp
Peanut	2010	377.496	583.287	397	0,07	%
	2020	516.904	866.932	625	0,07	%
	2010-2020 change	36,93%	48,63%	57,33%	0,004	pp.pp
Plantain	2010	260.301	3.182.184	N.D	N.D	%
	2020	506.440	4.493.285	2.890	0,06	%
	2010-2020 change	94,56%	41,20%	N.D	N.D	pp.pp
Yucca	2010	270.787	3.808.239	13	0,0003	%
	2020	401.959	5.779.727	4.306	0,075	%
	2010-2020 change	48,44%	51,77%	33025%	0,074	pp.pp
Beans	2010	285.858	353.729	4.515	1,28	%
	2020	302.571	369.048	1.862	0,50	%
	2010-2020 change	5,85%	4,33%	-58,76%	-0,77	pp.pp
Cucumber	2010	186.080	194.017	3	0,0015	%
	2020	275.333	258.987	1	0,0003	%
	2010-2020 change	47,96%	33,49%	-75,00%	-0,001	pp.pp
Cotton	2010	145.000	405.200	53.929	13,31	%
	2020	225.000	1.095.321	155.895	14,23	%
	2010-2020 change	55,17%	170,32%	189%	0,92	pp.pp
Cowpeas	2010	249.486	146.145	N.D	N.D	%
	2020	221.929	181.929	N.D	N.D	%
	2010-2020 change	-11,05%	24,49%	N.D	N.D	pp.pp
Oil palm	2010	112.430	2.642.640	6.478	0,25	%
	2020	219.683	3.484.963	1.262	0,04	%
	2010-2020 change	95,40%	31,87%	-80,51%	-0,21	pp.pp
Taro (cocoyam)	2010	185.402	1.470.000	N.D	N.D	%
	2020	218.017	1.683.771	20	0,001	%
	2010-2020 change	17,59%	14,54%	N.D	N.D	pp.pp
Pumpkin	2010	135.990	158.591	N.D	N.D	%
	2020	152.444	178.269	N.D	N.D	%
	2010-2020 change	12,10%	12,41%	N.D	N.D	pp.pp

(Sources: MINADER, 2018; MINADER, 2020; IISD, 2020; Ritchie, 2021; Mpabe Bodjongo, 2022; Ritchie et al., 2022; CIFOR, 2023; IITA, 2023)

During the past five decades, there has been significant expansion in agricultural activities and their trade. The area devoted to the main crops increased to 3.8 million hectares from 2.9 mm ha (a 31% increase in a decade). Maize, plantain and cocoa have been the main drivers of this increase. Importantly, agricultural output has increased in more than 70%, showing not only an increase in area planted but especially an increase in productivity. Studies conducted by different authors confirm this assertion. Sotamenou and Nehgwelah (2018) found that between 1995 and 2015, the post-liberalization period, free trade policies in Cameroon made movement of agricultural products easier and thus an increase in agricultural production. Factors such as agricultural capital formation, foreign direct investment, permanent crop land, interest rates and the exchange rate also contributed towards an increase in the agricultural value added, driving agricultural expansion.

Ordway et al (2017) found that oil palm production has increased significantly in Cameroon. Seventy-three percent of survey respondents reported clearing forest, the magnitude of which was explained by differences in milling strategies and supply chain integration. Large-scale, non-industrial producers played a disproportionate role in deforestation, many of which were engaged in informal supply chains using non-industrial mills. Farms associated with more clearing tended to use high-yielding seedlings.

Folefack et al (2019) found that Cameroon is currently the 3rd largest African producer of palm oil, and 13th largest global producer. The country's more than 200,000 ha of mostly non-industrial oil palm plantations, which are often characterized by archaic production methods, will likely expand significantly by 2025. Their continued expansion represents a threat to forest landscapes, wildlife biodiversity and the environment.

Gilbert et al (2013) uncovered an increasing expansion in the cultivation of cash crops such as banana and cocoa with an increase in trade in these crops with the European Union and North America. Gbetnkom and Khan (2020) equally uncovered an increasing expansion of major cash crops such as cocoa, and banana with a corresponding increase in exports.

Nkendah (2010; 2013) found that Cameroon is the first trading partner of the Economic and Monetary Community of Central Africa (CEMAC) countries notably in agricultural and horticultural products. Interest in cross-border trade of agricultural and horticultural commodities between Cameroon and its neighbours has been overwhelming, but knowledge of its magnitude, determinants, and consequences remains inadequate, leading not only to undervaluation of figures in the national accounts, but also inhibiting formulation of appropriate policies and strategies to exploit its potential impact, particularly on food security. In 2008, a volume of just over 155 000 tons of agricultural and horticultural commodities has been shipped from Cameroon to its neighbours in the CEMAC for an estimated value of almost 38 billion CFA francs and representing 0,4% of GDP in Cameroon. Ofeh et al (2019) while investigating the implications of trade policy on agricultural growth in Cameroon found evidence that trade dependency ratio or trade openness has a positive and significant impact on agricultural growth in Cameroon only in the short run. Custom duty on its part has a negative significant effect in the short run while trade imbalance remains insignificant. Other indicators like inflation and real effective exchange rates have significant positive effects both in the short run and long run. Equally, intermediation margin and the interest rate on loans have short run positive and negative significant effects respectively. This implies the need for more financing in the sector from stakeholders.

Analyzing Cameroon's agricultural exports (both unprocessed crops and their derived products) for 2020 reveals that cocoa, cotton, banana, coffee, and rubber together accounted for 80% of the country's agricultural exports. Consequently, these last three products, which were not initially included in the list of crops with the largest harvested areas, were also examined in this analysis (Table 5). When comparing 2010 to 2020, it was found that cocoa had reduced its harvested area but increased both production and exports. Cotton, in contrast, showed an increase in harvested area, production, and exports. Banana and coffee decreased in harvested area and exports but remained important export products. Rubber is particularly notable as its harvested area and exports grew, yet its production volume declined.

Table 5 Comparison between 2010 and 2020 in terms of area, production, exports, and the export-to-production ratio for crops other than cocoa and cotton that account for 80% of Cameroon's exports

Crop		Harvested area (ha)	Production (tons)	Exports (tons)	Exports/Production	
Banana	2010	77.120	1.333.851	237.942	17,84	%
	2020	59.622	948.175	188.593	19,89	%
	2010-2020 change	-22,69%	-28,91%	-20,74%	2,05	pp.pp
Coffee	2010	214.348	66.584	48.097	72,24	%
	2020	60.569	29.793	21.417	71,88	%
	2010-2020 change	-71,74%	-55,26%	-55,47%	-0,35	pp.pp
Rubber	2010	53.767	54.864	32.852	59,88	%
	2020	58.039	47.100	32.031	68,01	%
	2010-2020 change	7,95%	-14,15%	-2,50%	8,13	pp.pp

Although only two export-oriented products—cocoa and cotton—are among the crops with the largest harvested areas, it would be inaccurate to conclude that Cameroon's agricultural production is solely for domestic consumption. In fact, export-oriented products collectively accounted for

14.35% of the total harvested area in Cameroon in 2020, indicating a significant focus on exports within a portion of the country's agriculture.

3.1.2 Change in commodity distribution

The areas where the key commodities are grown depend largely on the agroecological-climatic zones, however within these zones, there have been changes in distribution, summarised in Figure 3 and showing the change in area dedicated to the production of timber, cocoa, and oil palm, at the arrondissement level across Cameroon. There are a total of 360 arrondissements in the country. Timber data was obtained from the Global Forest Watch (GFW) database (<https://data.globalforestwatch.org/datasets/minfof:concessions-forestieres>), cocoa from MapSPAM (<https://mapspam.info>, IFPRI 2019), and oil palm from a recent publication by Descals et al. (2024) (<https://zenodo.org/records/11034131>).

Figure 3 Change in commodity area in Cameroon

Cocoa is mainly produced in the Southwest, Centre, Littoral and East regions of Cameroon, which together account for more than 90 percent of the national production (MINADER, 2018). The Southwest region is the largest producer, with about 40 percent of the total output.

Coffee is mainly produced in the West, Northwest and Southwest regions of Cameroon, which together account for more than 80 percent of the national production. The Western regions are the largest producers of coffee, with about 50 percent of the total output (MINADER, 2018).

Oil palm is largely produced in the Southwest, Littoral and South regions of Cameroon (MINADER, 2018), which together account for more than 80 percent of the national production. The Southwest region is the largest producer of oil palm, with about 40 percent of the total output.

Timber is harvested largely from natural forests and is sourced from across the southern humid zone, mainly in the Centre, South and East regions.

Plantain is mainly produced in the Southwest, Littoral, Centre and West regions of Cameroon, which together account for more than 80 percent of the national production. The Southwest region is the largest producer of plantain, with about 40 percent of the total output (MINADER, 2018).

Bananas are mainly produced in the Southwest and Littoral regions of Cameroon, which together account for more than 90 percent of the national production. The Southwest region is the largest producer of bananas, with about 60 percent of the total output (MINADER, 2018).

Maize is mainly produced in the Centre, Northwest, West and Far North regions of Cameroon, which together account for more than 80 percent of the national production. The Centre region is the largest producer of maize, with about 30 percent of the total output (MINADER, 2018).

Cotton is mainly produced in the Far North, North and Adamawa regions of Cameroon, which together account for more than 90 percent of the national production. The Far North region is the largest producer of cotton, with about 60 percent of the total output (Mesmin et al., 2021).

Rubber is mainly produced in the South and Southwest regions of Cameroon, which together account for more than 90 percent of the national production. The South region is the largest producer of rubber, with about 60 percent of the total output (MINADER, 2018).

3.1.3 Trade patterns

Agricultural crops play a vital role in Cameroon's economy, providing a significant source of income and export earnings. The country's primary export crops — banana, cocoa, coffee, rubber, and cotton — collectively contribute to more than 50% of national non-oil export revenues (Nkafu Policy Institute, 2022). Figure 4 illustrates the destination countries that account for 80% of exports for each of these products. While plantain, maize, and other food crops are primarily cultivated for domestic consumption, a portion of these crops is also exported to neighbouring countries.

Plantain, banana, maize and other food crops are mainly produced for domestic consumption, but some of them are also exported to neighbouring countries. Cameroon is the "granary" of Central Africa, as it accounts for 70% of intra-community trade in the Central African Economic and Monetary Community (CEMAC)(CIRAD, 2023).

Figure 4 Export destinations for banana, cocoa, cotton, coffee and rubber 2020

Source: FAO, 2020; FMI, 2022

Trade in agricultural crops is influenced by various factors, such as the agro-ecological diversity of the country, the quality and quantity of the production, the infrastructure and logistics, the market access and competitiveness, the policies and regulations, and the climate change and environmental impacts (Green Vision, 2014; Nkafu Policy Institute, 2022; CIRAD, 2023). Trade in agricultural crops also has social and economic implications for the producers, consumers and other stakeholders involved in the value chains (CIRAD, 2023).

3.1.3 Landscape patterns and processes

Figure 5a and b land cover maps are based on the Tropical Moist Forests (TMF) datasets (<https://forobs.jrc.ec.europa.eu/TMF>, with 30 m spatial resolution). They show the reduction and fragmentation of intact primary forest from 1990 to 2020 and resulting increase in degraded land, and change to deforested land around the major coastal urban areas of Douala, Limbe and, Kribi. From 2002 to 2023, Cameroon lost 976 kha of humid primary forest, making up 49% of its total tree cover loss in the same time period. Total area of humid primary forest in Cameroon decreased by 5.1% in this time period, and in 2020, Cameroon had 37.7 Mha of land above 10% tree cover, extending over 81.4% of its land area, and as of 2000, 17% of Cameroon's tree cover was intact forest (Global Forest Watch 2024).

Figure 5a Land cover change every 10 years between 1990 and 2020 across Cameroon

Figure 5b Map of forest transition typologies between 1990 and 2020 across Cameroon (30 m spatial resolution, derived from the TMF datasets).

Departments with the highest percentage of deforestation between 2010 and 2020 include Littoral Region, with Mungo County experiencing the highest deforestation in the region, followed by Wouri

and Sanaga-Maritime; Sud-Ouest Region where Kako experienced the highest deforestation, not only in the county but also in the entire country. It is followed by Meme, though at a significantly lower rate; Centre Region where Mfoundi County has the highest proportion of deforested area in the region and the second highest in the country. Notably, within the region, it is the county with the largest non-forest land. Mefou-et-Afamba is the second county in the region with the highest deforestation. Departments where the area of intact forest in 1990, then deforested in 2020, is one standard deviation above the mean include Mbam-et-Kim, Haut-Nyong, Lom-et-Djérem, Dja-et-Lobo, Sanaga-Maritime, Océan, Nyong-et-Kellé, Nyong-et-Mfoumou and Mefou-et-Afamba. Departments where the area of secondary forest in 1990, then deforested in 2020, is one standard deviation above the mean include Lom-et-Djérem, Kadey, Mbam-et-Kim, Noun, Mbéré and Mbam-et-Inoubou.

Figure 6 Change in the proportion land area under land cover categories of intact (primary) forest, degraded (secondary) forest, forest regrowth, deforested land, non-forest land, and water, within each department in regions, Cameroon

3.1.4 Commodity biodiversity risk analysis

Figure 7 Commodity risk for Cameroon's forests (a) Change in tree cover every five years between 2000 and 2020, and (b) Association between tree cover change and the expansion of timber production, cocoa, and oil palm at arrondissement level

We analysed changes in tree cover every five years from 2000 to 2020 and examined the relationship between these changes and the expansion of timber production, cocoa cultivation, and oil palm cultivation in Cameroon. Our findings reveal that the expansion of these land uses was significantly associated with increased tree cover loss during this period (Figure 6b).

Between 2000 and 2020, arrondissements experiencing a 1% increase in timber production area were associated with an average 3.74% increase in tree cover loss (95% Confidence Interval [CI]: 2.64%–4.84%) (Figure 2b). Similarly, a 1% increase in cocoa cultivation area every five years was linked to a 0.03% increase in tree cover loss on average (CI: 0.01%–0.05%). For oil palm cultivation, a 1% increase in cultivation area every five years was associated with a 1.16% increase in tree cover loss on average (CI: 0.95%–1.36%).

These results underscore the differential impact of land use types on forest loss, with timber production and oil palm cultivation having much larger effects compared to cocoa cultivation. The findings highlight the critical need for targeted policy interventions to balance economic development with sustainable forest management in Cameroon, especially in regions experiencing rapid expansion of timber, cocoa, and oil palm activities.

(b) Species vulnerability and crop expansion

Figure 8 Commodity risk on Cameroon's species (a) Species richness, landscape pressure, and species vulnerability index calculated by multiplying species richness and landscape pressure, and (b) Association between these biodiversity-related metrics and the expansion of timber production, cocoa, and oil palm at arrondissement level

We examined the relationships between species richness, landscape pressure, species vulnerability, and the expansion of timber production, cocoa cultivation, and oil palm cultivation at the arrondissement level across Cameroon. Our analysis reveals notable spatial patterns in the association between biodiversity and agricultural or industrial expansion during the 2000–2020 period.

The expansion of timber production, cocoa cultivation, and oil palm cultivation was more pronounced in areas with high species richness (Figure 7 bii). This suggests that regions harboring a greater diversity of species are affected by land use changes linked to these industries. Notably, cocoa cultivation exhibited a unique pattern, with its expansion being more substantial in areas experiencing significant landscape pressure (e.g., habitat fragmentation and land-use intensification). This trend, however, was not observed for timber production or oil palm cultivation, which did not show strong associations with landscape pressure.

We found that the expansion of timber production, cocoa cultivation, and oil palm cultivation was concentrated in areas with high species vulnerability (Figure 7b(iii)). This means that areas where species are already at greater risk of extinction or population decline—due to limited ranges, environmental sensitivity, or other factors—have borne a disproportionate burden of land conversion for economic activities.

3.1.6 Literature review of main drivers of land use change

Agricultural expansion, timber and non-timber forest products, grazing, and settlements, infrastructure and mining all drive land use change in Cameroon, shown in Table 6.

Table 6 Summary of literature reviewed exploring drivers of land use change

Agroecological zone	Drivers of land use change	Recent studies
Sudano-Sahelian	Agricultural expansion	Epule et al., 2012; Tsozué et al., 2020; Yuh et al., 2023; Djosebe et al., 2023
	Settlement expansion	Yuh et al., 2023; Djosebe et al., 2023
	Over grazing	Chia et al., 2023
	Mining	Chia et al., 2023
Guinea high savannah	Agricultural expansion	Anjos et al., 2023
	Overgrazing	Gakou-Kakeu et al., 2023; Anjos et al., 2023
Western Highlands	Agricultural expansion	Takem-Mbi et al., 2013; Temgoua et al., 2018a; Tellen and Yerima, 2018; Toh et al., 2018; Feldt et al., 2020; Fokeng et al., 2020; Fogang et al., 2021; Shegwe et al., 2021; Ewane et al., 2023; Nguedia et al., 2023; Gakou-Kakeu et al., 2023; Fopa et al., 2023;
	Settlement expansion	Olayiwola et al., 2011; Takem-Mbi et al., 2013; Kimengsi et al., 2017; Fokeng et al., 2020; Fogang et al., 2023; Nguedia et al., 2023; Fopa et al., 2023;
	Overgrazing	Toh et al., 2018; Feldt et al., 2020; Shegwe et al., 2021;
	Over exploitation of timber and non-timber forest products	Takem-Mbi et al., 2013; Fokeng et al., 2020
Mono-modal rainforest	Agricultural expansion	Ajonina et al., 2014; Bruggeman et al., 2015; Asaha et al., 2016; Beckline et al., 2018; Mahmoud et al., 2019; Fogang et al., 2021; Ewane et al., 2021; Tagne et al., 2022; Tene et al., 2023; Gakou-Kakeu et al., 2023; Ghong et al., 2023;
	Timber exploitation companies	Tene et al., 2023
	Infrastructure development	Gakou-Kakeu et al., 2023
	Exploitation of timber and non-timber forest products	Mahmoud et al., 2019; Tagne et al., 2022; Ghong et al., 2023
	Settlement expansion	Ewane et al., 2021; Tagne et al., 2022;
Bimodal rainforest	Agricultural expansion	Bruggeman et al., 2015; Temgoua et al., 2018b; Zekeng et al., 2019; Ewane et al., 2020; Fogang et al., 2021; Tawe et al., 2022; Ndip et al., 2023; Gakou-Kakeu et al., 2023
	Infrastructure development	Yuh et al., 2019; Gakou-Kakeu et al., 2023
	Mining	Tchindjang et al., 2018; Rodrigue, 2019; Kamga et al., 2020; Nguemhe and Ayodele, 2020; Duna et al., 2021; Gakou-Kakeu et al., 2023
	Wanton exploitation of timber and non-timber forest products	Zekeng et al., 2019

Sustainable landscape initiatives

There have been several SLIs implemented in Cameroon, with the oldest being the Takamanda ToU.

Figure 9 Recent SLIs in Cameroon

Agroecological zones	Active SLI	References
Sudano-Sahelian	Operation Green Sahel	CIF (2017) Afrik21 (2022) CBD (2023)
	Riverbank Development Project in the Benue Catchment Area	
	Project -TRI "The Restoration Initiative (TRI)" MINEPDED	
Guinea high savannah	Adamawa Plateau Initiative (API) TRI "The Restoration Initiative"	FAO (2020) ERuDeF (2022)

Western highlands	The Rainforest Alliance “Championing Community-led Landscape Management in Cameroon”	Rainforest Alliance (2020) FAO (2020) GEF (2023)
	The Rainforest Alliance “Removing barriers to biodiversity conservation, land restoration, and sustainable forest management through community-based landscape management” Project (COBALAM)	
	INBAR landscape restoration projects	
Mono-modal rainforest	National REDD+ process	CIF (2017) Afriq21 (2022) SOWEDA (2023) PSMNR-SW (2023)
	Green, Inclusive and Sustainable Cities Initiative	
	South West Development Authority (SOWEDA)	
	PSMNR-SW	
Bimodal rainforest	ERP1	CIF (2017) IUCN (2022) Proforest (2022)
	GCLP	
	National REDD+ process	
	Technical Operational Units (TOU)	
	The Synergy Platform between Ngoyla-Mintom Actors (SYAMINGO)	
	Model Forests: Dja & Mpomo (FOMOD) and Campo-Ma’an (CAMAMF)	
	Grand Mbam (green cocoa) Landscape	
	Ayos Cluster Landscape	
	Forum of Dja Actors / Dja UNESCO Heritage site/ Dja Green cocoa landscape program and the roadmap to deforestation free cocoa The Synergy Platform between Ngoyla-Mintom Actors (SYAMINGO)	
	Tridom (Ngoyla Mintom) Landscape	
	TNS (Trinational de la Sangha)	
	API (Aménagement Pilote Intégré) de Dimako	
	Technical Operation Unit Takamanda	
	Technical Operation Unit South-East Cameroon	
	MEAO (Mission d'Etude d'aménagement de l'Océan)	

Discourses surrounding biodiversity and agriculture

Drawing on Ingram et al (2024) analysis of cocoa and deforestation discourses can be seen in terms of the diverse drivers perceived by multiple stakeholders in commodity value chains. Stakeholders include individuals, enterprises and organisations of farmers, cooperatives, cocoa traders and their associations, voluntary certification standards, and regulating local and national government organisations, traditional authorities, civil society, NGOs and researchers in forestry and land use planning sectors.

There has been strongly sectoral policy approach to cocoa and forests up until 2020, which has resulted in little alignment between stakeholders and policies, and subsequent incongruences between national and international policies, practices, perceptions, and geographic maps. Cameroonian government policies that seek to increase cocoa production have been little aligned with internationally driven policies aiming to protect forest, avoid and reduce cocoa driven deforestation, particularly the EUDR. Incongruences remain due to siloed policies on cocoa, forest and landuse planning. Farming practices on the ground do not fit neatly into these categories, instead operating on a fluid continuum from agriculture to cocoa agroforestry to forest. Private sector policies and practices – due to the nature of the international value chain emerging from Cameroon – were more aligned, with cocoa production, deforestation and maintaining farm level shade tree cover addressed by cocoa buyers and cooperatives mainly through voluntary sustainability certification and corporate programs. However, international zero deforestation

standards and practices were not well known by farmers in the fields and forests around Ntui. This has only just started to happen since 2022 with the politically laden Roadmap to Deforestation Free Cocoa and EU-Cameroon Cocoa Talks providing multistakeholder forums for exchange. However, these dialogues have not led to a consensus on definitions of chocolate (agro)forests, cocoa led deforestation or on how to address it. This situation is like the West African situation about five years ago, when the WCF Cocoa and Forest Initiative (World Cocoa Foundation, 2017) bringing governments, private sector and farmers organizations together to bridge and discuss deforestation in the protected area-forest-farm continuum. However, Cameroon has notable differences from West Africa, exemplified by the forest-rich Ntui study area with increasing deforestation and degradation, with forest-shaded cocoa agroforestry. Ghana and Cote d'Ivoire have much higher rates of historical deforestation, less forest and tree cover, such that the EUDR 2020 cut-off date constitutes a competitive advantage and creates few incentives for shaded cocoa agroforestry or restoration in practice. In practice there is nominal but scarce forest protection and little promotion of agroforestry, reforestation, or afforestation. The low reach of these policies to the ground in the Ntui area indicates little coherence between policies, perceptions and practices of farmers and other stakeholders on the ground.

A spatial analysis and ground verification (Ingram et al 2024) of the Central region in Cameroon where timber and cocoa are key commodities, suggest that policies have been ineffective in halting cocoa related deforestation, have been modestly effective in expanding cocoa production, and not effective in increasing cocoa yields. The significant unreliability of maps as a basis for decision making given the difficulties of distinguishing cocoa agroforests from natural forests was highlighted, with 64% of cocoa farms observed, shown as forested land on the open street map. This finding has significant implications for national and EU policymakers, particularly concerning the EU Deforestation Regulation, regarding setting the 2020 deforestation baseline and the accuracy of the EU's benchmarking system which categorizes 'third countries' or regions within countries into low, standard, or high risk based on their overall deforestation risk associated with all products covered by the Regulation (European Union, 2023).

Diverse drivers at local, national and global scale scales have contributed to cocoa-led deforestation. These include policies seeking to increase cocoa production to augment individual farmer incomes and state revenues. Concurrently policies and practices incentivize zero deforestation and protect forests. Other drivers of deforestation include poverty, low cocoa yields, land availability, migration, population growth, land and labour prices. Stakeholders believe opportunities to counter deforestation include yield improvements (although this could conversely encourage further deforestation), awareness raising, statutory and customary law enforcement in protected areas, and restricting land sales.

Cocoa farmers do not perceive themselves as responsible for deforestation, however their practices indicate that cocoa farming is a driver of deforestation, in the past in the degraded area south of Ntui and in the last decade in the forest area to the north. Apart from voluntary sustainability certification, farmers are little involved in or aware of the plethora of initiatives to counter deforestation, such as restoration or afforestation or reduce deforestation. The practice of shaded, agroforestry cocoa systems are incentivised by certification but not explicitly through other policies.

Whilst farmers perceive few trade-offs between their practices and forest use, NGOs, development and government authorities do perceive major trade-offs. Major paradoxes and trade-offs were apparent in the different policy narratives and with farmer's practices. This context of incoherent national and international policies and incongruence with farm and forest practices on the ground in Ntui presents dilemmas if any of the cocoa, forest, landuse planning and development related government and private sector policies are to be effective. Alignment, particularly between the EUDR and Cameroonian national policies and stakeholders is critical. Whilst the Roadmap and Cocoa Talks started to address multi stakeholder and sectoral alignment – these are not apparent on the ground in farmers practices. Explicit, political choices about the trade-offs between cocoa production, the resulting impacts on farmer's livelihoods and forest conservation are lacking. Given

the international, telecoupled nature of the cocoa value chain from Cameroon such trade-offs imply balancing state sovereignty on the related issues of land use planning, forests, trade and development, alongside customary land use and governance practices, with international value chain governance. Another dilemma this study exposes is the contentious politics of cartography. Ground verification showed major discrepancies between land cover classifications of forests and fields. Given the upcoming importance of geo-mapping cocoa farms and chain of custody and traceability requirements towards European markets, map-based land use planning requires maps that accurately reflect different types of land use cover in which cocoa production systems occur.

3.2 Colombia

3.2.1 Land use

Land use in Colombia is heavily dominated by cattle ranching, which occupies the largest portion of agricultural land. Between 2010 and 2020, land dedicated to cattle ranching expanded significantly, increasing by 26% over the decade. By 2020, cattle ranching occupied a total of 17,416,473 hectares (Figure C), underscoring its prominence in Colombian agriculture.

Agriculture is a cornerstone of Colombia's economy, contributing 8.44% to the national GDP (DANE, 2020). In 2020, the crops that covered 80% of Colombia's cultivated area included coffee, rice, oil palm, sugarcane, corn, plantain, cocoa, potatoes, bananas, and yucca (Table 7). Among these, corn, plantain, and yucca showed a decrease in harvested area when comparing 2010 and 2020. In contrast, other key crops experienced an increase in harvested area, reflecting growing demand and investment in these agricultural sectors. Oil palm showed the most significant expansion, with the largest increase in harvested area, followed by cocoa, bananas, rice, and coffee.

Crop	Harvested area (ha)	Production (tons)	Exports (tons)	Exports/Production		
Coffee	2010	778.052	535.380	434.085	81,08	%
	2020	844.744	833.400	729.774	87,57	%
	2010-2020 change	8,57%	55,67%	68,12%	6,49	pp.pp
Rice	2010	482.297	1.988.191	258	0,01	%
	2020	656.000	3.038.500	3.980	0,13	%
	2010-2020 change	36,02%	52,83%	1442,78%	0,12	pp.pp
Oil palm	2010	203.415	3.994.523	124.635	3,12	%
	2020	478.045	7.172.978	693.982	9,67	%
	2010-2020 change	135,01%	79,57%	456,81%	6,55	pp.pp
Corn	2010	522.237	1.421.868	13.543	0,95	%
	2020	345.069	1.392.895	43.230	3,10	%
	2010-2020 change	-33,92%	-2,04%	219,20%	2,151	pp.pp
Plantain	2010	368.754	2.978.461	110.793	3,72	%
	2020	264.106	2.300.810	141.029	6,13	%
	2010-2020 change	-28,38%	-22,75%	27,29%	2,41	pp.pp
Cocoa	2010	95.641	39.534	7.986	20,20	%
	2020	188.371	63.416	18.451	29,09	%
	2010-2020 change	96,96%	60,41%	131,04%	8,894	pp.pp
Potatoes	2010	108.308	1.867.899	783	0,04	%
	2020	125.426	2.625.272	1.245	0,05	%
	2010-2020 change	15,80%	40,55%	59,02%	0,01	pp.pp
Banana	2010	78.089	2.019.625	1.691.788	83,77	%
	2020	99.267	2.399.607	2.034.001	84,76	%
	2010-2020 change	27,12%	18,81%	20,23%	0,996	pp.pp
Yucca	2010	196.282	2.082.440	347	0,02	%
	2020	97.074	1.030.750	882	0,09	%
	2010-2020 change	-50,54%	-50,50%	154,32%	0,07	pp.pp
Beef	2010	13.792.216	766.591	2.098	0,27	%
	2020	17.416.473	743.901	31.685	4,26	%
	2010-2020 change	26,28%	-2,96%	1410,25%	3,99	pp.pp

Table 7 Comparison between 2010 and 2020 in terms of area, production, exports, and the export-to-production ratio for crops representing 80% of the cultivated area in Colombia

Colombia is divided into six distinct ecological regions, that consider physical elements such as relief, climate, hydrography, vegetation, and soil type. Concurrently, Colombia is politically segmented into departments, serving as an intermediate government level between the nation and the local administration (i.e., municipalities). These departments hold autonomy in allocating

budgets and designing planning instruments. Each natural region encompasses multiple departments.

When it comes to export-oriented agriculture, coffee and bananas are Colombia's primary export commodities, with 87% and 84% of their production directed to international markets in 2020. While cocoa, oil palm, and plantain also contribute to exports, they play a more secondary role compared to coffee and bananas. Collectively, these crops—coffee, bananas, oil palm, and plantain—accounted for 80% of Colombia's agricultural exports in 2020, highlighting their significant impact on the country's trade landscape. Importantly, exports have risen across all major crops with extensive harvested areas, suggesting an increasing emphasis on meeting international demand.

Although sugar is not among the crops with the largest harvested areas, shown in Table 8, it remains a significant export product, justifying a closer look at sugarcane production. Findings indicate that the area dedicated to sugarcane cultivation has expanded, as has overall production, pointing to sustained demand domestically and internationally.

Crop	Harvested area (ha)	Production (tons)	Exports (tons)	Exports/Production		
Sugar cane	2010	348.531	32.538.975	804.951	2,47	%
	2020	407.583	36.364.744	760.725	2,09	%
	2010-2020 change	16,94%	11,76%	-5,49%	-0,38	pp.pp

Table 8 Comparison between 2010 and 2020 in terms of area, production, exports, and the export-to-production ratio for sugar cane in Colombia

3.2.2 Change in commodity distribution

Colombia has six distinct ecological regions, that consider physical elements such as relief, climate, hydrography, vegetation, and soil type. Concurrently, Colombia is politically segmented into departments, serving as an intermediate government level between the nation and the local administration (i.e., municipalities). These departments hold autonomy in allocating budgets and designing planning instruments. Each natural region encompasses multiple departments. The areas where the key commodities are grown in Colombia depend largely on the agroecological-climatic zones, however within these zones, there have been changes in distribution notably an expansion of in the areas growing bananas and oil palm, summarised in Figure 12. There are 1,122 municipalities in the country. Export bananas, coffee, and oil palm data was obtained from the Agricultural Municipal Evaluations (EVA) conducted by the Ministry of Agriculture (MINAGRICULTURA).

Figure 10 Change in area dedicated to the production of export bananas, coffee, and oil palm at municipality level, Colombia

Cattle is the most prevalent primary activity in Colombia, practiced in every region and increasing significantly since 2016, shown in Figure 11. Antioquia leads in number of hectares (1.573.938 hectares). More land is being used for cattle ranching in the Eastern plains and the Amazon region, with concerns about the illegality of this expansion (conducted by large owners in public lands and national parks) and threatening the swaths of continuous forests and natural savannahs.

Figure 11 Area dedicated to cattle ranching , Colombia

Coffee covers the largest area of all crops in Colombia, shown in figure 12, and is grown in the Andean region in the centre of the country at or above 1,500 meters of elevation. Coffee cultivation experience an 8.57% expansion from 2010 to 2020. Figure 16 shows changes in land cultivation by department: coffee shrank in the western part of the country in favour of growth in the Southern and eastern Andes. This change has been documented and explained by changes in consumer preferences towards shade grown and high-quality coffee (Rueda and Lambin 2013).

The cultivated area of rice witnessed a 23,7% increase during the 2010-2020 period. Over this timeframe, the Orinoco region consistently held the position of having both the largest rice cultivation area and experiencing the highest growth. In 2010, Meta (27,29%) and Casanare (18,35%) were the leading departments in rice cultivation. However, by 2020, this dynamic had shifted. Casanare dominated, cultivating 41,33% of the total rice cultivation area in the country, with Meta following at 18,66%. Notably, Vichada, a department also located in the Orinoco region, exhibited the most substantial growth in cultivated areas during the 2010-2020 period.

Oil palm has seen the most drastic increase in area, shown in figure 12. It is grown in the Eastern plains, the Caribbean region and the Magdalena valley that crosses the country from South to North. The departments dominating the oil palm cultivation landscape maintained their dominance between 2010 and 2020. Meta (in the Eastern plains) secured the top spot with the largest area, followed by Magdalena and Cesar in the Caribbean region. The most remarkable expansion in cultivated areas occurred in Córdoba (27,87%) and Sucre (20,21%), both in the Caribbean region.

Cocoa is produced across the Andean region. Santander is the primary producer, closely followed by Nariño and Antioquia. Cocoa cultivation has seen substantial growth in the Amazonia region, with the department of Guainía experiencing the highest increase during the 2010-2020 period, boasting a growth rate of 11,72%.

Banana production is concentrated in the Caribbean region. Antioquia accounts for 40,17% by 2020, followed by Magdalena.

Figure 12 Area harvested for the main agricultural commodities, Colombia

3.2.3 Trade patterns

Agriculture is the second-largest contributor to exports, representing 25,35% of the country's total export volume. It was surpassed by gas and oil, which accounted for 42,86% (DANE, 2020). Shown in Table 9, coffee, bananas, and cocoa exhibited the highest export-to-production ratios, followed by oil palm and beef.

Table 9 Total production and total exports, Colombia

		Production (tons)	Exports (tons)	Exports/Production	
Coffee	2010	535.380	434.085	81,08	%
	2020	833.400	729.775	87,57	%
	2010-2020 change	55,67%	68,12%	6,49	pp
Rice	2010	1.988.191	258	0,013	%
	2020	3.424.119	3.981	0,116	%
	2010-2020 change	72,22%	1443,02%	0,103	pp
Oil palm	2010	3.994.523	124.635	3,12	%
	2020	7.172.978	693.982	9,67	%
	2010-2020 change	79,57%	456,81%	6,55	pp
Cocoa	2010	39.534	7.986	20,20	%
	2020	63.416	18.451	29,09	%
	2010-2020 change	60,41%	131,04%	8,89	pp
Banana	2010	2.019.625	1.691.788	83,8	%
	2020	2.399.607	2.034.001	84,8	%
	2010-2020 change	18,81%	20,23%	1,0	pp
Beef	2010	766.591	2.098	0,27	%
	2020	743.901	31.685	4,26	%
	2010-2020 change	-2,96%	1410,25%	3,99	pp

Source: FAOSTAT (2023)

Shown in figure 13, the primary destinations for Colombia's most significant agricultural exports are predominantly European countries, with the United States standing out as an exception. The U.S. is the largest importer of Colombian plantains and coffee, highlighting its strong trade relationship with Colombia in these staple products. Within Europe, countries such as Spain, Germany, Belgium, and Italy are significant markets for Colombian agricultural exports, reflecting the growing demand for these products in the European Union. Belgium plays a key role as the top importer of Colombian bananas. Similarly, the Netherlands emerges as the leading destination for oil palm products, underscoring the strategic position of Colombian oil palm within the European vegetable oil and biofuel markets.

Figure 13 Export destinations for Colombian banana, plantain, coffee and oil palm 2020

Source: FAO, 2020; FMI, 2022

3.2.4 Landscape patterns and processes

Figure 14 shows land cover maps based on the Tropical Moist Forests (TMF) datasets (<https://forobs.jrc.ec.europa.eu/TMF>, with 30 m spatial resolution. They show a gradual loss of intact primary forest from 1990 to 2020 and increase in deforested land. From 2002 to 2023, Colombia lost 1.99 Mha of humid primary forest, making up 39% of its total tree cover loss in the same time period. The total area of humid primary forest in Colombia decreased by 3.6% in this time period. In 2010, Colombia had 81.3 Mha of natural forest, extending over 72% of its land area. In 2023, it lost 188 kha of natural forest, equivalent to 119 Mt of CO₂ emissions. As of 2000, 72% of Colombia land cover was >30% tree cover. As of 2000, Colombia had 81.8 Mha of tree cover, equivalent to 72% of its land area and 2.0% of the global total and 42% of Colombia's tree cover was intact forest. In 2020, Colombia had 84.7 Mha of land above 10% tree cover, extending over 77.9% of its land area (Global Forest Watch 2024).

Figure 14 Land cover change every 10 years between 1990 and 2020 across Colombia

The Andes region has experienced the highest percentage of deforestation relative to its total area among all regions in Colombia. This trend has been ongoing since 1990, with deforestation intensifying over the decades. The period from 2010 to 2020 recorded the highest deforestation rates, affecting the majority of departments within the region. This pattern reflects the persistent pressures on Andean forests, driven by expanding agricultural frontiers, urbanization, and infrastructure development—factors emblematic of the region's complex socio-economic dynamics.

Deforestation, however, is not exclusive to the Andes. Other regions have exhibited similarly concerning trends. In the Amazon region, which holds Colombia's largest expanse of primary forests, the departments of Putumayo, Caquetá, and Guaviare have experienced particularly severe deforestation. In the Orinoquía region, the departments of Arauca and Meta also stand out for significant forest loss during the same period. These trends align with agricultural and livestock expansion between 2010 and 2020. In Orinoquía, crops such as oil palm and rice have increased considerably, while cattle farming has expanded in the Amazon region (figure 15). This agricultural and livestock intensification highlights mounting pressures on areas of critical ecological importance and biodiversity.

Despite these concerning trends, there has been a significant positive development in forest regrowth. The Andes region has emerged as the area with the highest percentage of forest recovery in Colombia during the 2010–2020 period. This regrowth, unmatched by any other region, can be attributed, among other factors, to the abandonment of agricultural lands, which has created conditions for natural forest regeneration. This recovery underscores the resilience of Andean ecosystems and highlights the potential for landscape restoration when agricultural pressures are reduced.

The dynamics of coffee production are influenced by various variables. Rueda and Lambin (2013) observed that market trends are emerging as significant forces shaping local landscapes. The growing demand for high-quality and sustainable coffees is now a driving factor in land-use decisions among Colombian farmers. Those who cater to differentiated markets not only capture a larger portion of the value added but also face lower volatility compared to mainstream producers. Regions suitable for producing differentiated coffees have witnessed a notable increase in the planted area. These underlying factors may elucidate the observed decrease in harvested area in some Colombian regions and the concurrent increase in others.

Murillo-Sandoval et al. (2023) present compelling evidence highlighting cattle ranching as the primary driver of forest loss beyond the legal agricultural frontier. Despite prevailing stereotypes associating cattle drivers with motives beyond beef production, such as territorial control, the profitability of ranching extends beyond mere economic considerations. While there is validity to these perceptions, a comprehensive understanding of the widespread presence of cattle in rural landscapes necessitates an exploration of the economic and productive rationale behind ranching (Van Ausdal, 2009). The spatiotemporal dynamics governing the expansion of cattle are shaped not only by agrarian policies but also by broader contextual factors, including the War on Drugs in Colombia and the 2016 peace accord (Murillo-Sandoval et al., 2023). Appreciating the intricate interplay of these elements is crucial for a nuanced comprehension of the multifaceted landscape of cattle-related activities.

The proliferation of oil palm plantations has emerged as a significant catalyst for biodiversity decline in tropical regions (Vargas et al., 2015). Often at the expense of forested areas, the expansion of oil palm plantations raises substantial environmental concerns. Colombia, ranked as the fifth-largest global producer of oil palm, has implemented subsidy-oriented policies to secure a pivotal position in forthcoming biodiesel markets (Castiblanco, Etter & Aide, 2013). Colombia's expansion, particularly in palm oil production for biodiesel, was driven by policies catering to a domestically controlled biofuel market led by national palm oil producers. The evidence indicates that this expansion involved diverse land control practices constituting forms of 'accumulation by dispossession' and 'assimilation.' These practices are intricately linked to contextual factors such as Colombia's agrarian history, the ongoing armed conflict, and government policies (Marin-Burgos, 2017).

For the categories of intact forest and secondary forest (Figure 16), our analysis reveals notable patterns of deforestation between 1990 and 2020. The departments where the area of intact forest in 1990—later deforested by 2020—was one standard deviation above the mean include Caquetá, Antioquia, Meta, and Guaviare. Similarly, for secondary forest, the departments where the area in 1990—later deforested by 2020—was one standard deviation above the mean are Antioquia, Norte de Santander, Meta, and Caquetá. These findings highlight regions with significant forest loss across both intact and secondary forest categories.

Figure 15 (a) Map of forest transition typologies between 1990 and 2020 across Colombia (30 m spatial resolution, derived from the TMF datasets), and (b) the proportion of different typologies at the department levels in the Pacifico, Caribe, Andes, Orinoquia, and Amazonia regions (see Table 1 for detail extent for each department)

3.2.5 Commodity biodiversity risk analysis

We analysed the relationship between changes in tree cover and the expansion of oil palm, export banana, and coffee cultivation at the municipality level across Colombia from 2000 to 2020. Our findings indicate that the expansion of these agricultural commodities was significantly associated with increased tree cover loss during this period (Figure 17b).

Between 2000 and 2020, municipalities experiencing a 1% increase in oil palm cultivation area every five years were associated with an average 0.22% increase in tree cover loss (95% Confidence Interval (CI): 0.04%–0.40%) (Figure 17b). Similarly, a 1% increase in export banana cultivation area every five years was associated with an average 0.44% increase in tree cover loss (CI: 0.02%–0.87%). In the case of coffee cultivation, a 1% increase in cultivated area every five years corresponded to an average 0.42% increase in tree cover loss (CI: 0.31%–0.52%).

These results underscore the impact of agricultural expansion on forest cover across Colombian municipalities. While oil palm cultivation contributed to modest but measurable tree cover loss, export banana and coffee cultivation showed comparatively stronger associations with deforestation, reflecting potential differences in land-use intensity or geographic patterns of expansion.

Figure 16 Commodity risk on Colombia's forests. (a) The change in tree cover every five years between 2000 and 2020, and (b) the association between tree cover change and the expansion of oil palm, export banana, and coffee cultivation at the municipality level across Colombia.

We investigated the relationships between species richness, landscape pressure, species vulnerability, and the expansion of export banana, coffee, and oil palm cultivation at the municipality level across Colombia from 2000 to 2020. Our analysis revealed distinct patterns in how these crops expanded relative to ecological and environmental factors.

First, we observed no significant correlation between the expansion of export banana and coffee cultivation and areas of high species richness during this period (Figure 17a). In contrast, oil palm expansion predominantly occurred in areas characterized by low species richness, suggesting a preference for ecologically less diverse regions.

Second, there was no observed relationship between the expansion of export banana and coffee cultivation and indicators of landscape disturbance, such as habitat fragmentation or land-use change intensity (Figure 17(ii)). However, oil palm cultivation expanded more rapidly in areas with limited landscape pressure, indicating that this crop's growth has primarily taken place in regions with lower existing levels of human-induced landscape alteration.

Finally, oil palm expansion was associated with areas of low species vulnerability, suggesting that oil palm cultivation may be less concentrated in regions where species are highly sensitive to environmental changes (Figure 17b(iii)). Conversely, no discernible trend was observed between the expansion of export banana and coffee cultivation and species vulnerability.

These findings highlight key differences in the spatial patterns of agricultural expansion for these crops. The expansion of oil palm appears to avoid regions with high species richness and vulnerability while favouring areas with lower landscape pressure. On the other hand, the lack of clear correlations between export banana and coffee expansion and ecological variables may reflect the more widespread or historically established nature of these crops in Colombia.

(b) Species vulnerability and crop expansion

Figure 17 Commodity risk on Colombia's species. (a) Species richness, landscape pressure, and species vulnerability index calculated by multiplying species richness and landscape pressure, and (b) the association between these biodiversity-related metrics and the expansion of export banana, coffee, and oil palm cultivation at the municipality level, Colombia.

3.2.6 Literature review of main drivers of land use change

Cropland and pasture conversion are the primary drivers of land use change in Colombia (Eraso et al., 2011; Armenteras et al., 2011), with some regional variability. Armenteras et al. (2013) assert that in the Caribbean region, illicit crops and livestock dominate as key drivers, while in the Orinoquia region (Eastern plains), it is predominantly crops. In the Chocó forest biodiversity hotspot (i.e., in the Pacific coast), Anaya et al. (2020) identify commercial logging, agricultural frontier expansion, mining, and illicit crops as major contributors. Armenteras et al. (2019) specifically pinpoint pasture conversion as the predominant factor in the Colombian Amazon.

Recent studies have explored alternative causes of land use change. Vanegas-Cubillos et al. (2022) identify development policies addressing conflict and post-conflict issues as influential factors, along with the enhanced market access highlighted by Hänggli et al. (2023). This suggests that deforestation drivers extend beyond agriculture and economic factors but are also linked to armed conflict, particularly the eradication of illicit crops and waves of migration resulting from the displacement of communities (Hoffman et al., 2018).

The historic impact of coffee production on land change during the late 20th century in Andean regions has been highlighted (Guhl, 2008). However, the dynamics of coffee production are influenced by several variables. For instance, Ibañez, Muñoz-Mora, and Verwimp (2013) discovered a

negative correlation between the risk of violence, the presence of illegal crops, and the decision regarding the percentage of the farm allocated to coffee, showing that more peaceful regions saw an increase in coffee cultivation. Rueda and Lambin (2013) observed that market trends are emerging as significant forces shaping local landscapes, especially the growing demand for high-quality and sustainable coffees. Those who cater to differentiated markets not only capture a larger portion of the value added but also face lower volatility compared to mainstream producers. Regions suitable for producing differentiated coffees have witnessed a notable increase in the planted area, while more conventional forms of production (i.e., sun-exposed monocrops of homogenous varieties) have seen a reduction in area planted.

Murillo-Sandoval et al. (2023) present compelling evidence highlighting cattle ranching as the primary driver of forest loss beyond the legal agricultural frontier. Despite prevailing stereotypes associating cattle drivers with motives beyond beef production, such as territorial control and rent extraction (Hecht 2019), the profitability of ranching does play an important role, supported by public policies and tax-free (illegal) land occupation. A comprehensive understanding of the widespread presence of cattle in rural landscapes necessitates an exploration of the economic and productive rationale behind ranching (Van Ausdal, 2009). The spatiotemporal dynamics governing the expansion of cattle are shaped not only by agrarian policies but also by broader contextual factors, including the War on Drugs in Colombia and the 2016 peace accord (Murillo-Sandoval et al., 2023). Appreciating the intricate interplay of these elements is crucial for a nuanced comprehension of the multifaceted landscape of cattle-related activities.

The proliferation of oil palm plantations has emerged as a significant cause of biodiversity decline in tropical regions (Vargas et al., 2015). Often at the expense of forested areas, the expansion of oil palm plantations raises substantial environmental concerns. Colombia, ranked as the fifth-largest global producer of oil palm, has implemented subsidy-oriented policies to secure a pivotal position in forthcoming biodiesel markets (Castiblanco, Etter & Aide, 2013). Colombia's expansion, particularly in palm oil production for biodiesel, was driven by policies catering to a domestically controlled biofuel market led by national palm oil producers. The evidence indicates that this expansion involved diverse land control practices constituting forms of 'accumulation by dispossession' and 'assimilation.' These practices are intricately linked to contextual factors such as Colombia's agrarian history, the ongoing armed conflict, and government policies (Marin-Burgos, 2017). Much of the expansion of palm occurred in already deforested lands, devoted to cattle ranching. The extent to which the displaced cattle production has contributed to deforestation in the Amazons and natural pastures conversion in the Eastern plains, is still a matter of debate that needs further scientific exploration.

Sustainable landscape initiatives

In Colombia, the European Union is supporting a large US\$ 245 million sub-regional project, **'Herencia Colombia' (HeCo) in the Caribbean and the Central Andes**,⁵ which since 2022 focuses on integrated territorial governance in sustainable landscapes. The project underscores socially and environmentally sustainable production models, aligning with national climate and biodiversity conservation goals. HeCo specifically aims to conserve natural ecosystems, reduce deforestation, and foster social inclusion through enhanced territorial governance, advocacy for public policy, and the encouragement of local sustainable development. This Caribbean landscape encompasses Departments like Magdalena, La Guajira, César, and Atlántico, featuring nine protected areas, two conservation strategies (OMEC), and 30 collectively titled areas (community councils of black communities, indigenous reserves, and peasant reserve zones). The region's mosaic includes marine-coastal areas and vital ecosystems like mangroves, tropical dry forests, and the country's primary coastal wetland. Interventions in this area target (a) the improvement of structural and

⁵ <https://updates.panda.org/securing-colombias-natural-heritage>

functional connectivity between existing protected areas and (b) the reduction of anthropogenic pressures, primarily associated with deforestation, land-use change, and unsustainable activities impacting ecosystem resilience. The landscape of the Central Andes encompasses the Páramo Los Nevados complex and its influence area in the Coffee Axis region. The primary objective is the ecological restoration of high-mountain ecosystems, coupled with efforts to enhance productivity, facilitate commercial agreements for community initiatives related to dairy, tourism, tubers, and vegetables, and support the effective management of protected areas and their surroundings. In addition to the Caribbean and Central Andes landscapes, the HeCo program is implemented in other three land areas (Corazón Amazonía, Transición Orinoquía, and Pacífico Marino-Costero) and four marine areas (Santuario de Flora y Fauna Malpelo; Santuario Fauna Acandí, Playón, Playona; Cordillera Beata; and Colina y Lomas, Cuenca Pacífico Norte). Partners in HeCo include conservation organisations like WWF and WCS

The Llanos Orientales area encompasses a megadiverse landscape with 20% land covered by protected areas, 30% communal lands and reforestation programs. It faces agricultural expansion for palm oil, cattle ranching, national and export trade. Violence, illicit economies, and weak state presence, appropriation of public lands, encroachment into natural parks, local elites driving deforestation, displacement of smallholders are major problems. Conservation and SLI include the **Colombia-Orinoquia Integrated Sustainable Landscape Initiative (OSILP)**, from 2017 to date and includes the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development and WWF⁶ This SLI has medium-high levels of telecoupling palm oil, banana and coffee to EU, and agroforestry and commercial forestry products, cattle, cashew, cocoa, dairy production, and palm oil. The SLI supporting capacity building for the implementation of integrated land-use planning and improved governance for deforestation control; sustainable land-use management through generating information, capacities, and incentives to reduce AFOLU GHG emissions from unsustainable land use and land-use changes in the agriculture, forestry, and other land uses (AFOLU) sector; providing technical assistance for the preparation of the Emission Reductions program and biocarbon fund for results-based payments and develop Colombia's capacity for robust monitoring, reporting, accounting, and verification of AFOLU emissions and removals; and Financing project coordination, management, monitoring, and evaluation activities.

The Magdalena Department is highly biodiverse from sea, dry tropical forest. The area has a long history agricultural expansion for banana, cocoa and oil palm export trade, violence, illicit economies, labour equity and working conditions, and weak state presence. Conservation projects and SLIs here are the **Cesar, Huila and Magdalena, Colombia PPI compacts**⁷ with IDH; SAN, ISEAL & Swiss State Secretariat Blueprint for Sustainable landscape. This landscape has high levels of telecoupling of cocoa, palm oil, banana and coffee to EU. The SLI aims to support commitments to deforestation-free cocoa in 2018, where Colombia was the first Latin-American country to do so. IDH works with the Board of AgroColombia Productiva y Sostenible and other stakeholders in the Protection, Production, Inclusion (PPI) compacts in the departments of Cesar, Huila and Magdalena.

Discourses surrounding biodiversity and agriculture

Biodiversity

Human decisions and behaviours with the natural ecosystem are also shaped by the various ways in which diverse values are attributed to biodiversity within policymaking. Identifying the prevailing discourses surrounding biodiversity allows us to understand how economic and political decisions have predominantly favoured specific values of biodiversity (MARINA-project; IPBES). For this reason, a content analysis was conducted to assess the values and definitions featuring the terms

⁶ <https://www.biocarbonfund-isfl.org/programs/orinoquia-sustainable-integrated-landscape-program>

⁷ <https://www.idhsustainabletrade.com/landscapes/colombia/>

biodiversity (MARINA-project). Arias Arevalo et al. (2017) suggests that the diverse ways in which people relate to biodiversity can be categorized into three broad classes: instrumental values, intrinsic values, and relational values. The definitions are as follows:

Instrumental values refer to biodiversity being seen as mere means to an end (sustaining livelihood, needs, and wants). These values are often measured in monetary terms. "The value of an entity as merely a means to an end". However, these values also extend to maintaining life and supporting livelihood services, particularly within market frameworks and conservation programs that involve treating nature as a commodity and privatizing rights (Chan et al., 2016).

Intrinsic values: pertain to the appreciation of biodiversity as ends in themselves and are frequently framed as moral duties. "The value of nature, ecosystems, or life as ends in themselves, irrespective of their utility to humans".

Relational values: encompasses the relationships and responsibilities between people and the natural environment. "The importance attributed to meaningful relations and responsibilities [...] between humans and nature".

These definitions are taken as a reference framework to determine what value, and to what extent, is being assigned to biodiversity in the Development Plans. It is crucial to recognize that these interpretations of nature are not mutually exclusive and can be expressed together in diverse combinations.

This analysis reveals that, in general, development plans primarily assign an instrumental value to biodiversity. However, there are specific instances where intrinsic value is acknowledged, particularly concerning unique ecosystems like coral reefs or paramo ecosystems. Conversely, when the plans refer to "land," they tend to emphasize its instrumental value. The term "land" overlooks the ecosystems present in the geographical area and is viewed primarily as capital for generating economic returns.

Agriculture

We conducted a content analysis to assess the values and definitions associated with "agriculture" in the NDPs. The various perspectives on how agriculture is understood can be categorized into three main categories:

Agriculture for Development: Agricultural productivity plays a central role in fostering development (Gollin, Parente & Rogerson, 2002; Johnston & Mellor, 1961).

Agroecology: Applying ecological concepts and principles to the design and management of agroecosystems. It aims to emulate the structure and function of natural ecosystems to create agroecosystems that rely minimally on high agrochemical and energy inputs (Altieri, 2004).

Agricultural Innovation: Utilizing science and innovation to enhance the environmental performance of intensive agricultural systems, steering them toward sustainability objectives, ensuring food security, and enhancing farmer livelihoods (Gaffney et al., 2019).

The agricultural discourse in the three development plans aligns with the Agriculture for Development perspective, viewing agriculture as a "driver of development." This perspective is based on the belief that large-scale agriculture fosters economic growth and job creation.

Law 160 of 1994 stipulates that uncultivated lands in Colombia should be allocated to poor farmers without other rural lands. However, under the Agriculture for Development perspective, the National Development Plan 2010-2014 (Law 1450) amended Law 160 to allocate contracts to agricultural companies for extensive farming development. Similarly, the NDP 2014-2018 proposed

an additional amendment to Law 160, allowing contract recipients to use the land as an asset for income-generating activities.

In 2012, the Constitutional Court declared these amendments unconstitutional, as they favored companies with significant economic capacity to acquire the uncultivated lands meant for rural workers. Nonetheless, Law 1776 of 2016 permitted private companies to receive uncultivated lands under concession within the Agriculture for Development framework. As a result, there has been land grabbing, not linked to land ownership but to the control companies exert over these resources (Torres-Mora, 2020).

Key agricultural and environmental policies

Our analysis revealed that the main policy of the Ministry of Agriculture was the “Analysis, Design, and Construction of Irrigation and Drainage Districts at the National Level (Land Improvement Fund),” aimed at managing water resource availability for agricultural development. For the Ministry of Environment, the primary policy was the “National Water Policy and Implementation,” which focuses on comprehensive water resource management.

3.3 Kenya

3.3.1 Land use

In 2020, the food crops occupying 80% of Kenya's cultivated area were corn, beans, tea, cowpeas, sorghum, potatoes, pigeon peas, wheat, and coffee (Table B). Within this group, tea, sorghum, wheat, and coffee stand out as the most export-oriented crops. Coffee is notable for its high export share, as most of its production is dedicated to international markets, focusing exclusively on the export of green coffee beans rather than derived products (Table 10). We have not included non-food crops such as horticulture.

Crop		Harvested area (ha)	Production (tons)	Exports (tons)	Exports/Production	
Corn	2010	2.008.346	3.464.541	11.707	0,34	%
	2020	2.135.741	3.789.000	8.325	0,22	%
	2010-2020 change	6,34%	9,37%	-28,89%	-0,12	pp.pp
Beans	2010	689.377	390.598	3.599	0,92	%
	2020	1.147.709	774.365	26.301	3,40	%
	2010-2020 change	66,48%	98,25%	630,79%	2,48	pp.pp
Tea	2010	171.916	1.735.000	417.661	24,07	%
	2020	269.400	3.050.000	575.509	18,87	%
	2010-2020 change	56,70%	75,79%	37,79%	-5,20	pp.pp
Cowpeas	2010	168.273	72.274	-	-	%
	2020	239.131	264.160	5.814	2,20	%
	2010-2020 change	42,11%	265,50%	-	-	pp.pp
Sorghum	2010	225.782	164.066	49.709	30,30	%
	2020	219.657	315.000	77.208	24,51	%
	2010-2020 change	-2,71%	92,00%	55,32%	-5,79	pp.pp
Potatoes	2010	121.542	2.725.936	874	0,03	%
	2020	176.252	1.859.776	27.229	1,46	%
	2010-2020 change	45,01%	-31,77%	3015,42%	1,432	pp.pp
Pigeon peas	2010	158.746	103.324	-	-	%
	2020	133.525	123.627	16.648	13,47	%
	2010-2020 change	-15,89%	19,65%	-	-	pp.pp
Wheat	2010	160.043	511.994	34.287	6,70	%
	2020	132.231	404.700	154.676	38,22	%
	2010-2020 change	-17,38%	-20,96%	351,12%	31,523	pp.pp
Coffee	2010	160.000	42.000	44.370	105,64	%
	2020	119.700	36.900	46.397	125,74	%
	2010-2020 change	-25,19%	-12,14%	4,57%	20,09	pp.pp

Table 10 Comparison between 2010 and 2020 in terms of area, production, exports, and the export-to-production ratio for crops representing 80% of the cultivated area in Kenya.

Tea was the only crop to expand in harvested area during this period, while sorghum, wheat, and coffee experienced reductions in cultivated land. Despite these declines, all four crops saw significant increases in their exports-to-production ratios, which may reflect Kenya's growing emphasis on agricultural exports. Wheat, in particular, is striking, with its export-to-production ratio increasing by 31.5 pp., underscoring a strong pivot towards export-driven production even amidst reduced planting.

Tea farming has witnessed significant expansion over the past decade, reaching 269,400 hectares by 2020 marked by notable increases in cultivation area (a 56.7% increase in a decade).

Avocado production in the last decade exhibited fluctuations, albeit with an overall positive trajectory. From 2010 to 2015, harvested area experienced a decline of almost 2,000 ha. (from 10.320 to 8.486 ha.) Between 2015 and 2020, a reversal of this trend occurred, and area expanded from 8.486 hectares to 24.447 hectares.

As the global demand for avocados is increasing and its profitability is much higher than the one of other tropical fruits, more farmers are planting the fruit. In addition, the Kenyan government is actively supporting avocado production by providing free seedlings to farmers and subsidizing small-scale plantations.

Banana production has experienced a decline over the decade. Area shrunk from 83.462 hectares to 60.718 hectares. Although there was a subsequent increase in the cultivated area from 60.718 hectares to 72.123 hectares between 2015 and 2020, it remained below the level recorded in 2010, indicating a reduction of 15,72%.

Pyrethrum cultivation has witnessed a substantial contraction, experiencing a 132.65% reduction in the cultivation area from 2010 to 2020. Despite this decline, there has been a noteworthy resurgence in production between 2020 and 2021 (75.7%). This positive upturn can be credited to the collaborative efforts of County governments, processors, individual propagators, inter-farm collaborations, and other industry stakeholders who have actively engaged in the distribution of planting materials.

The horticulture industry in Kenya is comprised up of flowers, vegetables, and fruits. Data on area cultivated are available, and export value data indicates strong growth in flowers (that accounted for 70 percent of the total export value, vegetables and fruits) (See trade section for more details). French beans production saw a moderate increase in area planted between 2018 and 2020 from 7.942 ha to 8.180. Volume also increased to 83.530MTs from the initial 66,765. Kenya has continually faced the challenge of pests and diseases increasing the cost of production. Additionally, the exceedance of pesticide residues has resulted in high rejection or interception in the export market (AFA, 2020).

3.3.2 Change in commodity distribution

Figure 18 shows the change and growth in areas dedicated to the production of tea at the constituency level and avocado at the county level across Kenya from 2005 to 2015. There are a total of 47 counties and 290 constituencies. Tea data was obtained from MapSPAM (<https://mapspam.info>, IFPRI 2019), and avocados from the Horticulture Validated Report published by the Agriculture and Food Authority of Kenya (AFA) (<https://statistics.kilimo.go.ke>).

Figure 18 Change in commodity area for tea and avocado in Kenya

3.3.3 Trade patterns

The production and trade of key commodities have all increased in Kenya in the period 2010 to 2020, shown in Table 8.

Tea production and exports in Kenya have seen significant growth, expanding by 42.71% and 30.89%, respectively. Despite the overall increase in production, there has been a slight reduction in exports.

The avocado sector has experienced substantial growth, with production increasing by 59.45%. Unfortunately, data on avocado exports for 2010 is unavailable from the FAOSTAT portal, preventing a comprehensive analysis of export behaviour during that period. Nevertheless, Kenya currently holds the 8th position globally in terms of avocado exports. The global demand for avocados is on the rise, and their profitability surpasses that of other tropical fruits (Agriculture and Food Authority, 2022). Projections indicate a significant market expansion from US \$1.70 billion to US \$2.70 billion between 2018 and 2024 (Ramos-Aguilar et al., 2021 and Nyakang'i, 2023).

Banana production has increased by 17.28% from 2010 to 2020 and, along with tea, stands out as one of the main crops. But bananas are predominantly cultivated for own consumption, and the percentage of bananas exported remains relatively low.

Unfortunately, data on pyrethrum exports for 2020 is unavailable from the FAOSTAT portal, making it difficult to analyse exports. Nonetheless, there is a noticeable 38.53% reduction in the tons of pyrethrum produced, declining from 462 in 2010 to 284 in 2020.

The vegetable export market in Kenya is dominated by French beans, snow peas, runner beans, and Asian vegetables. Most of the French beans produced in Kenya are exported. It is the main source of income for small-scale farmers. Kenya is the second-largest exporter of green beans to Europe (Kok, 2019). The European Union and the United States of America are the leading export markets for the Kenyan French beans accounting for approximately 75% of the total exports per annum (Markup, 2022). The European countries include France, the Netherlands, Belgium, and Germany (Masiga et al., 2014).

Table 11 Production and exports of main commodities – Kenya

		Production (tons)	Exports (tons)	Exports/Production	
Tea	2010	1.735.000	417.635	24,07	%
	2020	2.476.000	546.637	22,08	%
	2010-2020 change	42,71%	30,89%	-1,99	pp
Avocado	2010	202.294	*	*	%
	2020	322.556	79.069	24,51	%
	2010-2020 change	59,45%	*	*	pp
Banana	2010	1.583.143	96	0,01	%
	2020	1.856.658	13	0,00	%
	2010-2020 change	17,28%	-86,46%	-0,01	pp
Pyrethum	2010	462	3	0,65	%
	2020	284	*	*	%
	2010-2020 change	-38,53%	*	*	pp

Source: FAOSTAT (2023)

Kenya's key export products include tea, oil palm, coffee, wheat, sorghum, and avocado. Notably, oil palm and avocado are the only crops among these export leaders that do not rank among the crops with the largest cultivated areas. Shown in Figure 19, export destinations vary depending on the product, with European countries being the main export destination for coffee and avocado.

Figure 19 Export destinations for Kenyan tea, wheat, oil palm, sorghum, coffee and avocado (Source: FAO, 2020; FMI, 2022)

3.3.4 Landscape patterns and processes

Figure 20 shows land cover maps are based on the Tropical Moist Forests (TMF) datasets (<https://forobs.jrc.ec.europa.eu/TMF>, with 30 m spatial resolution). The counties most affected by deforestation are concentrated in the Central and Rift Valley regions of the country. In the Central region, Murang'a and Nyeri see the highest rates of deforestation, but these counties also show

significant forest regrowth. While Kirinyaga and Nyandarua exhibit regrowth to a lesser extent, Kiambu stands out with forest regrowth surpassing the percentage of deforested area.

In the Rift Valley region, the pattern is similar. Kericho, Elgeyo-Marakwet, and Bomet lead in terms of deforestation rates. However, Kericho has experienced regrowth almost matching its deforested areas, while Elgeyo-Marakwet has slightly lower regrowth compared to deforestation. Remarkably, Bomet has managed to achieve a regrowth rate that exceeds its deforestation percentage, signaling a strong recovery in forest cover.

Government interventions played a critical role in curbing deforestation, beginning around 2010, prior to the promulgation of the new constitution. The introduction of this new constitution made it significantly harder to convert forest land into private land, leading to a marked improvement in forest conservation. In addition, various tree-planting campaigns initiated by the government and community-led efforts have further contributed to increasing forest cover.

Figure 20 Land cover change every 10 years between 1990 and 2020, Kenya

Figure 21 Forest transition typologies between 1990 and 2020, Kenya (30 m spatial resolution, derived from the TMF datasets).

Figure 22 Proportion of different forest transition typologies at department levels, Kenya

An analysis of deforestation trends between 1990 and 2020, based on the categories of intact forest and secondary forest, reveals significant spatial patterns of forest loss across various counties. For intact forests the counties with deforested areas measuring one standard deviation above the mean

are Turkana, Narok, and Marsabit. These counties represent the regions where the loss of pristine forest cover has been significantly higher than average, highlighting critical hotspots and long-term pressures on ecosystems. For secondary forests (forests that had undergone regrowth or recovery in 1990 but were subsequently deforested by 2020), the analysis identifies Baringo, Narok, Kericho, Elgeyo-Marakwet, Nakuru, Nyeri, and Lamu as the counties with areas one standard deviation above the mean. A particular concern is Narok County, which appears in both categories, making it a focal point for deforestation activities that target both intact and secondary forest areas.

Figure 23 The change in the proportion land area under land cover categories of intact (primary) forest, degraded (secondary) forest, forest regrowth, deforested land, non-forest land, and water, within each department. Kenya

3.3.5 Commodity biodiversity risk analysis

We conducted an analysis of changes in tree cover across Kenya at five-year intervals between 2000 and 2020, focusing on the relationship between these changes and the expansion of tea and avocado cultivation at both the county and constituency levels. The results indicated no significant correlation between the increase in tea cultivation area and changes in tree cover at the constituency level, with a p-value of 0.12 (Figure 23b). This suggests that tea expansion has neither positively nor negatively influenced tree cover in the regions studied during the two decades.

In contrast, avocado cultivation showed a notable positive association with tree cover gains. Specifically, our findings revealed that for every 1% increase in the area dedicated to avocado cultivation at the county level over a five-year period, there was a corresponding 3.17% increase in tree cover gain during the same timeframe. This association was statistically significant, with a Confidence Interval (CI) ranging from 2.00% to 4.36%.

Fruit trees were introduced to enhance food security, increase tree cover, and improve biodiversity. The government's efforts also aimed to curb the expansion of exotic tree species along riverbanks, promoting more sustainable land use practices.

Figure 24 Commodity risk on Kenya's forests. (a) Change in tree cover every five years between 2000 and 2020, and (b) association between tree cover change and the expansion of tea and avocado at the county or constituency level, Kenya

We investigated the relationships between species richness, landscape pressure, species vulnerability, and the expansion of tea and avocado cultivation at the county and constituency levels across Kenya, focusing on trends from 2000 to 2020 (Figure 24). Our analysis revealed distinct patterns regarding how these crops interacted with ecological and landscape characteristics. The results showed that tea and avocado cultivation expanded more prominently in areas with high species richness. While this suggests a link between biodiversity and agricultural suitability, it also raises concerns about the potential pressures placed on these biodiversity-rich areas by expanding agricultural frontiers. Interestingly, we found no significant relationship between the expansion of tea and avocado farming and overall landscape pressure. Indicators such as land-use intensity, deforestation rates, or habitat fragmentation did not appear to be significantly associated with the areas where these crops were being cultivated. A notable finding was the link between tea farming and areas of high species vulnerability. Tea cultivation often expanded into regions where species were already under greater ecological risk, such as areas with endemic or endangered species. This trend suggests that tea farming may disproportionately target ecologically sensitive regions, potentially exacerbating risks to vulnerable species and their habitats. In contrast, avocado cultivation showed no significant association with species vulnerability, indicating that its expansion was less concentrated in ecologically fragile areas. This difference between the two crops may reflect varying land-use practices or the different environmental requirements of tea and avocado farming.

(b) Species vulnerability and crop expansion

Figure 25 Commodity risk on Kenya's species. (a) Species richness, landscape pressure, and species vulnerability index calculated by multiplying species richness and landscape pressure, and (b) the association between these biodiversity-related metrics and the expansion of tea and avocado at the county or constituency level, Kenya

3.3.6 Literature review of drivers of land use change

Changes in land use in Kenya are primarily driven by the intersecting human demands for exploiting, managing, and conserving land resources (Magige, 2018). Numerous studies underscore that a combination of multiple drivers contributes to these changes in land use (Dewan et al., 2012; Meshesha et al., 2016; Munthali et al., 2019). These human-induced factors leading to changes in land use can be broadly categorized into two major groups: proximate drivers and underlying drivers (Munthali et al., 2019). Forest degradation drivers include livestock grazing and wildlife population in some forest ecosystems especially in the dry lands (Hitimana et al., 2004, 2009a, 2009b).

Concerning underlying drivers, the Kenyan government has implemented various initiatives aimed at enhancing crop production. The launch of the Economic Recovery Strategy (ERS) in 2003 marked a significant step in revitalizing the agricultural sector. The ERS specifically aimed to boost economic growth, generate wealth and employment, eradicate poverty, and achieve food security. Recognizing agriculture as the pivotal productive sector for economic recovery, the strategy emphasized the revival of agricultural institutions and investments in agricultural research and extension as crucial for sustainable economic growth (GoK, 2010).

According to the Government of Kenya (GoK, 2010), the Sector Recovery Action Plan (SRA) was initiated in 2004 as a response to the ERS. The primary objective of the SRA was to transform Kenya's agriculture into a profitable, commercially oriented, and internationally and regionally competitive economic activity, providing high-quality, gainful employment to Kenyans. This transformation was

to be achieved within the framework of improved agricultural productivity and farm incomes while conserving the land resource base and the environment. The SRA set out to (i) Reduce the proportion of the population below the basic poverty line from 56 per cent in year 2000 to 26 per cent by 2010 and (2) Reduce the number of people who were food-cum-poverty stricken from 48.4 per cent to 23.5 per cent in 2008 and below 10 per cent in 2015. The proximate drivers are shown in Figure 26.

Figure 26 Drivers of land use change in Kenya

Agro ecological zone	Approximate Area in Km ² (%)	Characteristics of Agro ecological Zones	Drivers of Land Use Change	References
Agro-alpine regions	800 (0.1%)	This zone has no direct importance in agricultural production other than being the source of rain and some rivers/streams. It is confined to mountains and immediate surrounding such as Mt. Kenya and Mt Elgon	Agricultural expansion	Masayi, N.M., et al., 2022; Sang, C.C. et al., 2022; Rob Marchant, 2018
			Settlement expansion	Masayi, N.M., et al., 2022; Sang, C.C. et al., 2022; Rob Marchant, 2018
			Over grazing	Sang, C.C. et al., 2022
Highlands	53,000 (9.3%)	This zone is generally restricted to the highlands of Kenya between 1980 and 2700 m and occurs as a forest or open grasslands. This zone is found in the surrounding of Mt Kenya (parts of Meru, Embu, Kirinyaga, Kiambu, Muranga and Nyeri), isolated parts of the Rift Valley around Mau and Aberdares mountains (e.g around Kericho, Nandi and Nyahururu respectively), Kakamega, Vihiga, Kisii, Nyamira and the surrounding of Mt Elgon (e.g around Kitale and Bungoma County). The minimum rainfall is 1000 mm.	Agricultural expansion	Sang, C.C. et al., 2022 ; Rob Marchant, 2018
			Settlement expansion	Sang, C.C. et al., 2022 ; Rob Marchant, 2018
			Legal or illegal exploitation of timber and non-timber forest products	Jebiwott, A., et al. 2021;
Medium elevation	53,000 (9.3%)	This zone occurs mainly at elevations between 900-1800 m with annual rainfall between 950 and 1500 mm. Trees are numerous here and somewhat of shorter stature. This zone is the most significant for agricultural cultivation and several legume fodders are found here in crop-livestock systems. It is also the most resettled by human. It occurs in the vast parts of Nyanza, Western and Central provinces, good proportion of Central Rift-Valley (Nakuru, Bomet, Eldoret, Medium) and a small strip at the Coast region.	Agricultural expansion	Sang, C.C. et al., 2022; Rob Marchant, 2018; Onyango, D.O., et al., 2021;
			Settlement expansion	Sang, C.C. et al., 2022; Rob Marchant, 2018; Onyango, D.O., et al., 2021;
			Overgrazing	
			Legal or illegal exploitation of timber and non-timber forest products	Jebiwott, A., et al. 2021;
			Mining	Opiyo, S.B., Opinde, G., and Letema, S. (2022); Sang, C.C. et al., 2022
Semi-Arid	48,200 (8.5%)	This zone is much drier than Zone IV and occurs at lower elevations. Annual rainfall is 300-600. This Zone is prevalent in northern Baringo, Turkana, lower	Agricultural expansion	Sang, C.C. et al., 2022; Alemayehu, F. 2016; Rob Marchant, 2018; Clemens Greiner, 2016;

Agro ecological zone	Approximate Area in Km ² (%)	Characteristics of Agro ecological Zones	Drivers of Land Use Change	References
		Makueni, Kitui, Machakos, lower parts of Narok County and vast parts of North Eastern and coastal region.	Tourism	Sang, C.C. et al., 2022; Rob Marchant, 2018; Clemens Greiner, 2016;
			Settlement expansion	Sang, C.C. et al., 2022; Rob Marchant, 2018; Clemens Greiner, 2016;
Arid	300,000 (52.9%)	This zone is considered as semi desert and is the driest part of Kenya. Annual rainfall is 200-400 mm and is quite unreliable. The zone is found in Marsabit, Turkana, Mandera and Wajir counties.	Agricultural expansion	Sang, C.C. et al., 2022; Rob Marchant, 2018; Clemens Greiner, 2016;
			Infrastructure development	Sang, C.C. et al., 2022
			Mining	Sang, C.C. et al., 2022
Very Arid	112,000 (19.8%)	This is represented by Chalbi desert in Marsabit County. The Chalbi is a salt desert with very sparse salt bushes as the only vegetation found. It is vast and of beautiful scenery. Pastoralists use it as a source of mineral lick for livestock, particularly during the rainy season.	Settlement expansion	Sang, C.C. et al., 2022; Rob Marchant, 2018; Clemens Greiner, 2016;
Others (Waters etc.)	15,600 (2.6%)		Infrastructure development	Rob Marchant, 2018

Sustainable landscape initiatives

The **South West Mau Forest SLI**⁸ is led and partially funded by the Dutch Sustainable Trade Initiative (IDH), program to promote sustainable land use and improve the livelihoods of local communities while addressing environmental challenges. The initiative focuses on integrating sustainable agricultural practices, promoting responsible sourcing, and enhancing the management of natural resources. The SLI aims to restore and conserve 60,000 hectares of the forest by 2030. Key aspects of the SLI include collaboration, working with stakeholders, including government agencies, private sector companies, NGOs, and local communities, Nakuru, Kericho and Bomet national government agencies; tea, energy, telecommunications and timber companies; and civil society made up of NGOs and community groups, implementing partners and knowledge institutions to work together across the landscape. to create a multi-stakeholder approach to sustainable land management. Sustainable Agricultural Practices that increase productivity while minimizing environmental impact, are encouraged such as agroforestry, crop diversification, and soil health management. Landscape-Level Planning promotes integrated land-use planning that considers ecological, social, and economic factors to ensure that land use is sustainable and beneficial to all stakeholders. Market Engagement aims to facilitate connections between producers and markets that value sustainable practices, helping to create economic incentives for adopting environmentally friendly methods. Capacity Building is conducted by providing training and resources to local farmers and communities to enhance their knowledge and skills in sustainable practices.

The Mau forest– Masai-Mara river basin has seen several ongoing, long term initiatives which evolved into the **MaMaSe Sustainable Water Initiative**, an SLI from 2014-2017 and aimed at improving water safety and security in the Mara River Basin to support structural poverty reduction, sustainable economic growth and conservation of the basin’s ecosystems. Partners in the **MaMaSe project** included UNESCO, WWF, Wageningen University and University of Kabianga. The area

⁸ <https://www.idhsustainabletrade.com/initiative/isla-kenya/>

covers high biodiversity forests, savannah and wetlands with protected and conservation areas, important water catchment area with indigenous ethnic groups, community forests and water users associations. There has been expanding rice and fish farming lower Yala and Nyando Basins, grasslands with grazing systems, highlands tea-avocado-fruit-livestock-timber-NTFP, horticulture local, national and export trade, with medium levels of telecoupling of tea, avocado, horticulture products to EU.

Two conservation and sustainable landscape initiatives exist around Mt Kenya: The current 2020-2026 **Mount Kenya Sustainable Landscape and Livelihoods Programme** is financed and led by Ikea Foundation with Rainforest Alliance, the Kenya Tea Development Agency, Nature Kenya, Coffee Management Services and the Kenya Scouts Association⁹. This SLI builds on our earlier work in the region and now focuses on Kirinyaga County, Central Region and Embu County, Central Region, Kenya to bring communities, companies, government agencies, and institutions together to manage Mount Kenya's land and resources more sustainably, while improving farmer livelihoods. There is an emphasis on engaging local women and youth, and building the capacity of farmers and community members throughout the region to create equitable rural economies. Wageningen University has been involved in evaluating the impacts of the SLI (Berkhout et al. 2022). There is also the **Mt Kenya Forest Landscape Restoration** initiative led by CIFOR-ICRAF¹⁰. Key characteristics of the Mt Kenya landscape include it covering high biodiversity forests with conservation area: Mt Kenya National Park, Masai Mara National Reserve with indigenous ethnic groups. There are also grasslands (grazing systems) and coffee- tea-fruit-livestock-timber-horticulture systems, national and export trade. There are large areas high biodiversity forests, protected areas and extensive agriculture. There are medium-high levels of telecoupling tea, avocado, horticulture products to EU.

Discourses surrounding biodiversity and agriculture

Faling (2020) notes that in Kenyan policy, climate and agriculture are increasingly framed as interlinked. Climate-smart agriculture adoption is a continuation of an ongoing trend with the national Climate-Smart Agriculture Strategy seen as 'old wine in new bottles'. A frame discrepancy exists between strategic plans and sectoral policies, with policy frames influenced by donors, regional/global fora and personal networks. Faling policy frame analysis of the Ministries of Agriculture and Environment between 2002 and 2017 and interviews show how policy frames for agriculture, climate change, development, environment and food security have evolved over time, such that CSA is seen incremental shifting away from existing policy frames rather than being a radical transformation. There appears a discrepancy between Strategic Plans and sectoral policies, with strong influences from donors, regional and global fora and personal networks.

Entenmann et al (2014) looked at actors in the REDD+ implementation process in Kenya with regard to biodiversity conservation and monitoring. They found that, avoided deforestation in dry forests and enhancement of forest carbon stocks in different forest types were major activities and that that solving of socioeconomic issues was paramount for REDD+ implementation in general and for achieving additional conservation benefits. In REDD+ initiatives in dry forests, conservation objectives were primarily related to wildlife; actors stressed the importance of specific management measures to minimize human-wildlife conflicts. In initiatives to enhance forest carbon stocks, the sustained provision of timber, fuel wood and hydrological ES was regarded as a conservation priority and a prerequisite for project viability. Biodiversity indicators and monitoring schemes considered to be available by the actors were related to particular species. In conclusion, biodiversity in the context of REDD+ was framed as the resolution of socioeconomic and political issues. It was

⁹ <https://www.rainforest-alliance.org/in-the-field/mount-kenya-sustainable-landscape-and-livelihoods-program-project-profile/>

¹⁰ <https://www.cifor-icraf.org/knowledge/publication/33143/>

concluded that collaboration between Kenyan actors could contribute to the development of monitoring schemes for detecting REDD+ impacts on biodiversity and ES on a landscape scale.

5. Limitations

A major limitation of this study is the availability and quality of data, which posed challenges to analyzing historical agricultural practices in Cameroon, Colombia, and Kenya and their connections to international markets. Significant disparities in data availability exist across countries and at different spatial scales, affecting the depth and comparability of the analysis.

At the national trade level, the study primarily relied on data from FAOSTAT, which provides information on cultivated area (hectares), production volumes (tons), and exports (tons) for various crops. While FAOSTAT facilitated a broad analysis, its limitations must be noted. For instance, data on certain crops—such as avocado and cowpeas in Kenya or plantain and sorghum in Cameroon—are unavailable prior to 2010. This gap complicates efforts to track the historical expansion or contraction of these crops over the study period.

At localized scales, the data challenges are even more pronounced. Information on crop areas at the department or county level is sparse for most countries. A notable exception is Colombia, where access to the *Universidad de los Andes* municipal panel database provided detailed municipal-level data on cultivated hectares per crop. This dataset proved highly valuable, enabling an analysis of regional agricultural land-use trends and identifying areas where agricultural pressure is increasing or decreasing.

The study also relied on a 30-meter spatial resolution dataset to analyze significant landscape patterns, processes, and biodiversity risks. While this resolution is relatively detailed, it has limitations. For instance, it may fail to capture changes associated with smallholder crop systems, which are common in the study regions. Additionally, tree cover data may lead to misinterpretations, as some tree-covered areas could be classified as forests, even when they are part of agroforestry systems or plantations. Furthermore, the dataset does not provide detailed information about specific ecosystems, which restricts the ability to account for unique ecological contexts.

In the analysis of biodiversity risk, limitations arise from the reliance on species richness as the primary indicator. While species richness highlights the number of species present, it does not account for their endemism, rarity, or sensitivity to environmental changes. This could lead to an underrepresentation of biodiversity vulnerabilities, particularly in regions with high proportions of endemic or environmentally sensitive species.

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